

Prompt Governance in Financial AI: Comparative Performance of Structured Frameworks in Insurance and Investment Tasks

Hirbis Girolli

Independent Researcher, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

hirbis@finantor.com.br

February 2026

Classification: cs.CL (Computation and Language) | cs.AI (Artificial Intelligence) | q-fin.RM (Risk Management)

Keywords: prompt engineering, LLM evaluation, financial AI, hallucination, structured prompts, insurance risk, investment allocation, prompt governance, LLM-as-Judge

Abstract

Large Language Models (LLMs) are increasingly deployed in high-stakes financial domains, yet their output stability and factual reliability remain central concerns for insurers, investment platforms, banks, professionals, clients, and regulators alike. Despite a growing body of research on prompt engineering techniques, controlled empirical comparisons of structured prompt frameworks in domain-specific financial tasks remain scarce. We present the first systematic benchmark of four prompt governance approaches (Baseline zero-shot, Few-shot, CRISPE, and ACTFIT) across two representative financial tasks: life insurance risk classification and investment portfolio allocation. Using three commercial LLMs (Claude Sonnet 4.5, GPT-4.1, and Gemini 2.5 Flash), we evaluate 60 simulated cases through 2,160 API calls, measuring accuracy, hallucination rate, cross-run consistency, and a composite Efficiency Score. Evaluation employs two independent LLM judges from different model families (Claude Opus 4.6 and GPT-4o) with inter-rater agreement of $\kappa = 0.97$ for accuracy, validated by a stratified human sample ($n = 98$, $\kappa = 0.82$ judge-human). ACTFIT achieves 67.0% accuracy versus 44.9% for the baseline (+22.1pp), with particularly pronounced effects on investment tasks (+46.1pp). ACTFIT yields the highest Efficiency Score (0.537 vs. 0.342 baseline, +56.8%). GPT-4.1 combined with ACTFIT reaches the dataset peak: 81.7% accuracy with 0% hallucination at US\$ 0.006 per correct response. CRISPE produces a surprising negative finding: accuracy below the baseline (41.1% vs. 44.9%) with a 49.1% hallucination rate, demonstrating that poorly designed governance degrades performance. Our findings suggest that institutional prompt governance offers a cost-effective alternative to fine-tuning for financial applications, with implications for regulatory compliance and operational risk management.

1. Introduction

The deployment of Large Language Models (LLMs) in financial services has accelerated over the past two years, with applications spanning credit analysis, insurance underwriting, portfolio advisory, regulatory compliance, and client communication (Lee et al., 2024; Li et al., 2024; Nie

et al., 2024). These models offer notable capabilities in processing unstructured financial data, generating natural language explanations for complex decisions, and supporting human analysts in high-demand environments. The very characteristics that make LLMs powerful, however, also make them risky in domains where errors carry material financial consequences: their probabilistic generation, sensitivity to prompt formulation, and capacity to produce plausible yet factually unfounded outputs.

The problem of *hallucination* in LLMs (defined as the generation of fluent, syntactically correct content that is factually inaccurate or unsupported by the provided context; Bang et al. 2025; Ji et al. 2023) is particularly severe in financial applications. An insurance underwriting model that fabricates medical conditions, or an investment advisory system that invents historical returns, does not simply produce an incorrect answer — it produces a liability. Recent estimates suggest that LLM hallucination rates in financial natural language processing can reach 41% of responses in certain task configurations (FailSafeQA; Kamble et al. 2025), a threshold that would be unacceptable at any financial institution.

Two main approaches have emerged to mitigate LLM unreliability in specialized domains. The first is *model fine-tuning*, where a pre-trained LLM is further adjusted with domain-specific datasets to improve performance on targeted tasks (Araci, 2019; Hu et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2024). While effective, fine-tuning requires substantial computational resources, curated domain datasets, and ongoing maintenance as models are updated. These costs can be prohibitive for many financial institutions, particularly smaller ones. The second is *prompt engineering*, the systematic design of input instructions to guide LLM behavior without modifying model weights. Prompt engineering is immediately deployable and model-agnostic at a fraction of the cost, yet its effectiveness relative to fine-tuning and across different prompting strategies remains insufficiently studied in rigorous empirical settings.

A growing ecosystem of structured prompt frameworks has emerged to systematize prompt design. These frameworks (including STAR, CRISPE, CO-STAR, and ACTFIT, among others) propose standardized templates that decompose the prompting task into explicit components such as role definition, context provision, output format specification, and illustrative examples. Proponents argue that structured prompts reduce output variability and improve task adherence (Schulhoff et al., 2024). The situation, however, is curious: dozens of frameworks circulate in professional communities and commercial deployments, each with devoted advocates, yet **no published study offers a controlled, head-to-head empirical comparison of structured prompt frameworks in domain-specific financial tasks**. Existing benchmarks such as PromptBench (Zhu et al., 2023) focus on general NLP tasks and fail to capture the specific challenges of financial decision-making, where factual precision and regulatory compliance are non-negotiable.

This paper is, to our knowledge, the first to place these frameworks side by side in a controlled financial domain test. We compare four prompt governance approaches (Baseline zero-shot, Few-shot, CRISPE, and ACTFIT) across two representative financial tasks: life insurance risk classification and investment portfolio allocation. Our experimental design employs three commercial LLMs from leading laboratories (Claude Sonnet 4.5, GPT-4.1, and Gemini 2.5 Flash), 60 simulated cases of varying complexity, and three independent runs per configuration to measure consistency. Evaluation employs two independent LLM judges from different families, with human validation on a stratified subsample.

What this work delivers is straightforward: empirical evidence on what works and what does not when governing an LLM in a financial context; an evaluation methodology that goes beyond standard NLP metrics (BLEU, ROUGE, perplexity) to capture the dimensions that matter most to financial practitioners: factual accuracy, fabrication detection, and decision stability; and actionable guidance for financial institutions seeking to deploy LLMs with appropriate governance structures. In doing so, we position prompt engineering as a form of *institutional design* rather than mere technical optimization.

We begin by reviewing the literature on prompt engineering, meta-prompting, LLMs in finance, and output quality evaluation (Section 2). We then detail the experimental methodology, including framework operationalization, task design, dataset construction, the LLM-as-Judge protocol, and metrics (Section 3). Results are presented in Section 4, followed by a discussion of implications, limitations, and future research directions (Section 5). Section 6 concludes.

2. Related Work

2.1 Prompt Engineering: From Ad Hoc to Structured

The evolution of prompt engineering has progressed through several identifiable phases. Early work focused on zero-shot and few-shot prompting, demonstrating that task performance could be improved by providing examples within the input context (Brown et al., 2020). Chain-of-Thought (CoT) prompting introduced the technique of eliciting intermediate reasoning steps, producing substantial improvements on arithmetic and logical reasoning benchmarks (Wei et al., 2022). Subsequent refinements (Self-Consistency (Wang et al., 2022), Tree-of-Thought (Yao et al., 2023), and Least-to-Most prompting (Zhou et al., 2022a)) expanded the repertoire of available strategies for practitioners.

More recently, a distinct category of *structured prompt frameworks* has emerged, offering holistic templates that integrate multiple prompting dimensions into a cohesive system. CRISPE (Capacity, Role, Insight, Statement, Personality, Experiment) defines a roleplay-oriented structure emphasizing persona attribution and output style. CO-STAR (Context, Objective, Style, Tone, Audience, Response) provides a six-component template focused on communicative clarity. ACTFIT (Agent, Context, Task, Format, Illustration, Tone) proposes a governance-oriented architecture that frames prompt design as institutional design, with explicit definitions of the agent’s role, operational context, task specification, output format, illustrative examples, and communicative tone. Despite the proliferation of these frameworks in professional communities and commercial deployments, their comparative effectiveness has not been rigorously tested in controlled experimental settings.

The Prompt Report (Schulhoff et al., 2024) provides the most comprehensive survey of prompting techniques to date, cataloging over 50 distinct approaches. The survey is taxonomic rather than evaluative, however: it classifies techniques but does not provide head-to-head performance comparisons. Similarly, PromptBench (Zhu et al., 2023) offers an evaluation framework for LLMs but focuses on general-purpose benchmarks rather than domain-specific applications.

A complementary approach to manual framework comparison is automatic prompt optimization. DSPy (Khatab et al., 2024) proposes a declarative programming model that abstracts LLM

pipelines as computational graphs with parameterizable modules, using a compiler to automatically optimize these pipelines by maximizing a user-defined metric. DSPy demonstrated that concise programs can outperform both standard few-shot prompting and expert-crafted demonstration pipelines. Our work differs from DSPy in scope and level of abstraction: while DSPy optimizes prompts automatically via algorithmic search, we evaluate *manually designed* frameworks that encode institutional governance principles, a distinction analogous to the difference between automated hyperparameter optimization and deliberate architectural design.

On the model evaluation front, HELM (Liang et al., 2023) established a reference benchmark by evaluating 30 language models across 42 scenarios and 7 metrics (accuracy, calibration, robustness, fairness, bias, toxicity, and efficiency) under standardized conditions. HELM represented a fundamental advance in evaluation transparency. Both HELM and PromptBench, however, evaluate *models*; our work evaluates *prompt frameworks* while holding models constant and varying the instruction structure. This inversion of the analytical axis (from “which model is best?” to “which framework extracts the most from any model?”) is the central distinction of the present study.

Recent work addresses partial aspects of the question we investigate, but none covers the full intersection. Wang et al. (2024) proposed LangGPT, a programming language-inspired framework, and compared it against CRISPE and simple instructional prompts in writing and roleplay scenarios, but with subjective qualitative evaluation, no hallucination metrics, and a single model per configuration. Elnashar et al. (2025) conducted the methodologically closest study to ours, comparing six prompt formatting styles (JSON, YAML, CSV, prefix, function call, hybrid) across three LLMs (ChatGPT-4o, Claude, Gemini), measuring accuracy, token cost, and latency. Their comparison, however, targets output formats rather than governance frameworks that define role, context, process, and behavioral constraints, and does not measure hallucination. Mao et al. (2025) analyzed prompt template components in real-world LLMapps from companies like Uber and Microsoft, identifying co-occurrence patterns among elements such as Role, Context, and Output Format, a valuable descriptive study mapping what practitioners do, without evaluating what works best. He et al. (2024) showed that formatting variations (Markdown, XML, plain text) significantly impact GPT model performance and that larger models are more robust to such variations, a relevant finding about form that does not, however, test named frameworks with distinct design philosophies. Finally, Anh-Hoang et al. (2025) created an attribution framework separating prompt-caused hallucinations (Prompt Sensitivity) from model-intrinsic ones (Model Variability), testing five generic prompting techniques (zero-shot, few-shot, CoT, instruction, vague) across multiple LLMs. Their central finding (that prompt family weakly perturbs the hallucination rate relative to intrinsic model variability) creates a productive tension with our results, which we address in Section 5.1.

The present study differs from this literature in what it compares, how it compares, and where. The object of comparison is named governance frameworks with distinct design philosophies (restrictive governance vs. persona modulation), not generic prompting techniques or output formats. The method employs a full factorial design (4 frameworks \times 3 models \times 2 tasks \times 30 cases \times 3 runs) with a triad of metrics (accuracy, hallucination, and consistency), human validation, and cost analysis. The domain is financial, where hallucination carries measurable material consequences and ground truth is definable with precision.

2.2 Meta-Prompting and Orchestration Systems

An emerging line of work goes beyond the static prompt and proposes systems that orchestrate multiple LLM calls to solve complex tasks. The concept of *meta-prompting* (where one LLM is used to generate, evaluate, and refine prompts for another LLM or for itself) represents a paradigm shift: the prompt ceases to be the intelligence and becomes the *interface* through which model intelligence is accessed and channeled.

Zhou et al. (2022b) proposed the Automatic Prompt Engineer (APE), demonstrating that LLMs can optimize their own prompts via search over the instruction space. Fernando et al. (2023) extended this approach with Promptbreeder, a self-referential system in which prompts evolve through mutation and selection. More recently, Suzgun and Kalai (2024) formalized the Meta-Prompting concept, where an orchestrator LLM delegates sub-tasks to “specialized instances” of itself, each instructed with a specific persona and scope, a pattern resembling multi-agent design.

On the applied front, Poetiq AI (2025) demonstrated notable results with what it calls a “meta-system”: an orchestration layer that runs on top of frontier models without modifying them, using iterative loops of generation, self-evaluation, and refinement. The system achieved state-of-the-art on reasoning benchmarks (ARC-AGI-2: 54%, officially verified by the ARC Prize), knowledge extraction (HLE: 55%), and factual accuracy (SimpleQA Verified: 77.3%), surpassing the underlying base models in all cases. Three properties of the Poetiq meta-system are relevant here: automatic hierarchical segmentation of problems by type and complexity, with differentiated strategies per segment; self-auditing, where the system autonomously decides when a solution is satisfactory; and cross-model generalization: the learned strategies transferred to models released after the system’s training, indicating that the captured patterns concern *how to orchestrate reasoning*, not model-specific idiosyncrasies.

This literature situates our work at a specific position. While meta-prompting and orchestration systems operate at the level of the *call sequence* (multiple iterative interactions), structured frameworks like ACTFIT operate, in their original formulation, at the level of the *individual prompt* (a single carefully architected instruction). Both share the premise that structure in the application layer — not just raw model capability — determines output quality. Our experiment tests this premise at the fundamental level of the unit prompt; the extension to multi-call adaptive systems is a natural future direction discussed in Section 5.

2.3 LLMs in Financial Applications

The application of LLMs to financial tasks has been extensively reviewed in recent literature (Lee et al., 2024; Li et al., 2024; Mahdavi et al., 2025; Nie et al., 2024). Key application areas include sentiment analysis for market prediction, financial document summarization, credit risk assessment, fraud detection, and automated reporting. Domain-specific models such as FinBERT (Araci, 2019), BloombergGPT (Wu et al., 2023), and FinGPT (Yang et al., 2023) have demonstrated that financial specialization (whether through pre-training on financial corpora or fine-tuning on financial tasks) can produce significant performance improvements over general-purpose models.

Most research on financial LLMs has focused on model-level interventions (pre-training, fine-tuning, architecture modifications) rather than prompt-level governance. This asymmetry is

notable because prompt engineering is, in practice, the most immediately accessible lever available to financial institutions deploying commercial LLMs via API. A financial institution using Claude, GPT, or Gemini through their commercial APIs cannot modify model weights; it can only modify the instructions it sends. Understanding which prompting strategies maximize reliability in financial contexts is therefore of direct practical importance.

Insurance underwriting and investment allocation represent two tasks with complementary characteristics for benchmarking. Insurance risk classification requires categorical decision-making under uncertainty, with well-defined outcome classes and verifiable ground truth derived from actuarial tables and underwriting manuals. Investment portfolio allocation requires numerical output (percentages per asset class) with ground truth derivable from standard financial planning methodologies. Together, these tasks cover the spectrum from categorical to continuous outputs while remaining firmly within the regulated financial domain.

2.4 Output Quality Evaluation in LLMs

Standard NLP evaluation metrics (perplexity, BLEU (Papineni et al., 2002), ROUGE (Lin, 2004)) capture aspects of fluency and textual overlap but are poorly suited for evaluating financial decision quality. The hallucination evaluation landscape has evolved rapidly. TruthfulQA (Lin et al., 2022) established an early benchmark for factuality. More recent benchmarks including HaluBench (Ravi et al., 2024), HalluLens (Bang et al., 2025), and FailSafeQA (Kamble et al., 2025) have advanced hallucination evaluation in domains including finance, medicine, and general knowledge.

A methodological innovation relevant to the present work is the LLM-as-Judge paradigm, where language models are employed as automated evaluators of responses generated by other models. Zheng et al. (2023) demonstrated that LLMs can evaluate outputs with agreement exceeding 80% relative to human evaluators, and proposed protocols to mitigate positional and self-preference biases. Subsequent work refined the approach with multiple independent judges and inter-rater agreement measurement via Cohen’s Kappa.

Our evaluation protocol adopts this paradigm with two extensions. We use two LLM judges from different model families (Claude Opus 4.6 from Anthropic and GPT-4o from OpenAI) to mitigate intra-family bias, a documented risk when judge and evaluated model belong to the same provider. We also employ a conservative consensus rule: where judges agree, the consensus score is adopted; where they disagree, the more conservative score prevails (minimum accuracy, maximum hallucination). Human validation on a stratified subsample (~5% of cases, with oversampling of disagreements) anchors the credibility of the automated scores.

3. Methodology

3.1 Compared Frameworks

We compare four prompt governance approaches, selected to represent increasing levels of structural complexity. Table 1 summarizes the operationalization of each framework.

Note: Complete prompt templates for all four frameworks in both tasks are provided in Appendix A.

Table 1. Prompt frameworks compared in this study.

Framework	Structure	Operationalization	Complexity
Baseline	None (zero-shot)	Direct task instruction only. No role, context, format, or examples.	Minimal
Few-shot	Examples only	Task instruction + 2 worked examples with correct outputs. No role definition or format.	Low
CRISPE	6 components (Capacity, Role, Insight, Statement, Personality, Experiment)	Persona-oriented: defines agent capacity, role, and personality. Includes context and output statement. No explicit examples or format template.	Medium
ACTFIT	6 components (Agent, Context, Task, Format, Illustration, Tone)	Governance-oriented: defines agent competencies, operational context, explicit task with process, output format template, worked illustration, and calibrated tone.	High

The selection rationale is as follows. The **Baseline** (zero-shot) is the lower bound, representing the minimum-effort approach and default model behavior without any structural guidance. **Few-shot** adds only examples, isolating the effect of demonstration-based learning from the structural apparatus. **CRISPE** represents the class of persona-oriented structured frameworks that have gained traction in practitioner communities, emphasizing role definition and personality calibration. **ACTFIT** represents the class of governance-oriented structured frameworks that frame prompt design as institutional architecture, with explicit attention to all six components of the interaction. By comparing these four approaches, we cover the continuum from zero structure to comprehensive institutional governance.

A note on embedded examples: ACTFIT’s Illustration component contains **1 worked example** per task, a case with a complete output demonstrating the expected structure and reasoning. Few-shot, in turn, contains **2 examples** per task, including a diagnostic case deliberately selected to demonstrate override of conflicting criteria. ACTFIT thus operates with half the examples of Few-shot, but integrated within a broader governance architecture. CRISPE contains no explicit examples. This asymmetry is documented as a design variable; isolated component analysis, including expansion of the Illustration component, is proposed as future work (Section 5.7).

3.2 Benchmark Tasks

We evaluate framework performance on two financial tasks selected for their complementary characteristics and relevance to deployment contexts where LLM reliability matters most.

Task 1: Life Insurance Risk Classification. Given a client profile containing demographic information, medical history, lifestyle factors, and financial data, the model must classify the applicant into one of four risk categories: *Preferred* (lowest risk, best pricing), *Standard* (average risk, standard pricing), *Substandard* (elevated risk, premium surcharge), or *Declined* (unac-

ceptable risk, coverage denied). This task tests categorical decision-making under uncertainty, analogous to the initial triage performed by human underwriters at insurance companies.

Task 2: Investment Portfolio Allocation. Given an investor profile containing risk tolerance, investment horizon, financial goals, current assets, and constraints, the model must recommend an asset allocation expressed as percentages across predefined asset classes (e.g., equities, fixed income, alternatives, cash). This task tests numerical reasoning and the ability to generate internally consistent quantitative outputs, analogous to recommendations produced by financial consultants and robo-advisory systems.

These two tasks were chosen because they have verifiable ground truth derivable from established professional criteria, they represent both categorical and continuous outputs, they are directly relevant to regulated financial industries (insurance and wealth management), and they involve the type of structured reasoning where hallucination (fabrication of medical conditions, invention of financial products, or generation of mathematically inconsistent allocations) carries material consequences.

3.3 Dataset Construction

We constructed a dataset of 60 simulated cases (30 per task), distributed across three complexity levels: *simple* (10 cases), *medium* (12 cases), and *difficult* (8 cases). Table 2 describes the complexity criteria for each task.

Table 2. Complexity levels and case distribution.

Level	N per task	Insurance criteria	Investment criteria
Simple	10	Clear-cut profiles: young, healthy, no risk factors, or clearly uninsurable.	Straightforward goals, single horizon, standard risk tolerance.
Medium	12	Mixed profiles: some risk factors present, threshold between two categories.	Multiple goals, moderate complexity, some conflicting constraints.
Difficult	8	Complex profiles: multiple comorbidities, conflicting factors, borderline cases.	Complex constraints, multiple horizons, ethical/regulatory restrictions.

All cases were constructed with realistic profiles of Brazilian clients. Construction followed a three-stage process: profile generation based on demographic and financial distributions representative of the Brazilian market; ground truth determination using established professional criteria (actuarial underwriting guidelines for insurance; standard financial planning allocation models for investments); and complexity validation, ensuring each case was correctly classified and that difficult cases genuinely presented ambiguity or conflicting factors. The complete dataset is provided in Appendix B and the public replication repository.

3.4 Models

We tested three commercial LLMs: **Claude Sonnet 4.5** (Anthropic, `claude-sonnet-4.5`), **GPT-4.1** (OpenAI, `gpt-4.1`), and **Gemini 2.5 Flash** (Google, `gemini-2.5-flash`). These models were selected based on three criteria: commercial prevalence, as they represent three leading commercial LLM providers and are likely candidates for deployment in financial pro-

duction environments; API accessibility, as all three offer programmatic access with controllable parameters (temperature, max tokens); and parametric parity, as all accept temperature=0.3 and max_tokens=1500, enabling fair comparison.

Model selection was updated during the experimental setup phase due to API availability changes. Claude 3.5 Sonnet (originally planned) had been retired by Anthropic; GPT-5 (tested as an alternative) is a reasoning model that does not accept custom temperature. The final models represent three mid-tier commercial models from 2025, maintaining generational parity. Substitution details are provided in Appendix D.

We deliberately chose not to include open-source models (e.g., LLaMA, Mistral) in this initial benchmark. Our focus is on the most common deployment scenario at regulated financial institutions: commercial API-based access where the user controls the prompt but not the model weights.

3.5 Evaluation Metrics

We define four metrics (three component metrics and one composite) designed to capture the dimensions most relevant to financial AI deployment.

Table 3. Evaluation metrics.

Metric	Definition	Calculation	Range
Accuracy (A)	Proportion of responses matching the ground truth classification or allocation.	Correct / Total	[0, 1]
Hallucination Rate (H)	Proportion of responses containing fabricated information not present in the input case.	Hallucinated / Total	[0, 1]
Consistency (C)	Proportion of cases where all three independent runs produced the same output.	Unanimous / Total	[0, 1]
Efficiency Score (E)	Composite metric integrating accuracy, consistency, and hallucination resistance.	$(A \times C) / (1 + H)$	[0, 1]

The Efficiency Score captures the intuition that an ideal framework produces responses that are simultaneously accurate, consistent, and free of fabrication. The denominator $(1 + H)$ penalizes frameworks with high hallucination rates proportionally: a framework with 50% hallucination needs proportionally higher accuracy and consistency to achieve the same score. The metric reaches its theoretical maximum ($E = 1$) when accuracy and consistency are perfect and hallucination is zero.

Accuracy operationalization. For Task 1 (insurance), accuracy is binary: the model’s risk classification matches the ground truth category, or it does not. For Task 2 (investments), we define accuracy as the allocation falling within an acceptable tolerance band (± 5 percentage points per asset class) of the ground truth allocation, with total allocation summing to 100% ($\pm 2\%$).

Hallucination detection protocol. Each response is evaluated against the input case using a binary checklist. A response is marked as hallucinated if it references medical conditions, financial products, or historical data not present in the input; fabricates specific numerical values not provided; or attributes statements or policies to unmentioned sources.

3.6 Evaluation Protocol: LLM-as-Judge with Human Validation

The response volume (2,160) makes direct human evaluation impractical for all instances. We adopt the LLM-as-Judge paradigm (Zheng et al., 2023) with extensions designed to mitigate its known biases.

3.6.1 LLM Judges

Two independent judges from different model families evaluate each response:

Judge	Model	Provider	Persona	Temperature
Judge A	Claude 4.6	Opus Anthropic	Senior Life Insurance Underwriter (insurance) / Certified Financial Planner (investments)	0.0
Judge B	GPT-4o	OpenAI	Senior Life Insurance Underwriter (insurance) / Certified Financial Planner (investments)	0.0

Judge B selection was updated during the evaluation phase. The original design specified Gemini 3 Pro Preview (Google) as Judge B, covering all three families (Anthropic, Google, OpenAI). After three execution attempts, Gemini 3 Pro Preview exhibited recurring instability: JSON parsing errors in structured responses and billing-related interruptions after fewer than 150 completed evaluations. GPT-4o was selected as a replacement because it is widely used as an LLM judge in the literature (Zheng et al., 2023), its `response_format={"type": "json_object"}` parameter guarantees natively valid JSON output (eliminating parsing errors), and it belongs to the OpenAI family, maintaining family diversity on the judge panel.

Using judges from different families creates a bias control design, albeit with partial overlap: Claude Opus 4.6 (Anthropic) evaluates responses from its “sibling” Claude Sonnet 4.5 (potential intra-family bias), GPT-4o (OpenAI) evaluates responses from GPT-4.1 of the same family (potential intra-family bias), and Gemini 2.5 Flash occupies “neutral territory” (no same-family judge). This configuration enables detection and quantification of intra-family bias by cross-comparison: if both judges agree on a model, bias is dismissible; if they diverge systematically, bias becomes measurable (Section 4.6).

3.6.2 Output and Consensus

Each judge evaluates each response producing a binary JSON with two fields: **accuracy** (0 or 1) and **hallucination** (0 or 1), accompanied by justificatory notes.

Conservative consensus protocol. Where judges agree, the consensus score is adopted. Where they disagree, the conservative score prevails: minimum accuracy (accuracy = min of both judges) and maximum hallucination (hallucination = max of both judges). This conservative rule is deliberate: in a regulated financial domain, we prefer to err on the side of caution. The consequence is that all reported results constitute conservative estimates: actual performance may exceed what is reported.

3.6.3 Inter-Rater Agreement

Cohen’s Kappa is calculated between the two LLM judges for accuracy and hallucination separately, reporting global agreement and by subgroup (task, model, framework). Interpretation follows the Landis and Koch (1977) scale: $\kappa < 0.00$ (Poor), 0.00–0.20 (Slight), 0.21–0.40 (Fair), 0.41–0.60 (Moderate), 0.61–0.80 (Substantial), 0.81–1.00 (Almost Perfect).

3.6.4 Human Validation

Human validation on a stratified subsample anchors the credibility of the automated scores, serving two objectives: verifying the calibration of each LLM judge (which judge aligns more closely with human judgment) and empirically resolving any bias patterns detected through inter-rater agreement.

Form design. The validation form (v2.1) presents, for each case: the complete client profile (original case), the ground truth, the model response, and both judges’ scores. Including the original case is essential for hallucination assessment: without it, the evaluator would compare the response against the ground truth (measuring opinion divergence) rather than against the input (measuring factual fabrication).

Stratified sampling. From the 2,158 evaluated cases, we selected a sample of 170 cases distributed across three blocks, prioritized by informativeness:

Block	Criterion	N	Objective
1 — Calibration	Judges agree (acc and hal)	24	Verify baseline of human-machine agreement
2 — Accuracy	Judges disagree on accuracy	32	Arbitrate accuracy disagreements
3 — Hallucination	Judges disagree on hallucination	114	Arbitrate hallucination disagreements (proportional stratified sample across 4 disagreement patterns)

Block 3 was reduced from the original 421 hallucination disagreement cases to 114 by proportional stratified sampling (seed=42) across four disagreement patterns: P1 (A=hal, B=ok, acc=0), P2 (A=ok, B=hal, acc=0), P3 (A=hal, B=ok, acc=1), and P4 (A=ok, B=hal, acc=1). The rationale is that 80–100 stratified observations are sufficient for a reliable Cohen’s Kappa with acceptable confidence intervals.

Evaluator and saturation criterion. Validation was conducted by a single human evaluator (the author), who completed 98 of the 170 cases: Block 1 complete (24/24), Block 2 complete (32/32), and Block 3 partial (42/114). Evaluation was suspended at case 99 by saturation criterion: with 42 observations in Block 3, Cohen’s Kappa already showed a stable, convergent pattern between both halves of the sample (first 21 vs. last 21 cases), with no statistical drift, indicating that additional observations would yield diminishing marginal information. This criterion is analogous to the principle of *theoretical saturation* in qualitative research (Glaser and Strauss, 1967), adapted to the quantitative context.

Single evaluator limitation. We acknowledge that single-evaluator validation (the author) introduces potential bias. To mitigate this risk, we plan to distribute a blinded version of the form (without judge scores, to avoid anchoring bias) to external evaluators with professional experience in life insurance underwriting and/or financial planning. This external validation is documented as ongoing work and does not alter the results presented in this paper.

3.7 Experimental Protocol

The experiment follows a fully crossed design: 4 frameworks \times 2 tasks \times 30 cases \times 3 models \times 3 runs = **2,160 API calls**.

Table 4. Experimental parameters.

Parameter	Value
Models	Claude Sonnet 4.5, GPT-4.1, Gemini 2.5 Flash
Frameworks	Baseline, Few-shot, CRISPE, ACTFIT
Tasks	Life insurance risk classification, Investment portfolio allocation
Cases per task	30 (10 simple, 12 medium, 8 difficult)
Runs per configuration	3 (for consistency measurement)
Temperature	0.3
Max tokens	1,500
Total API calls	2,160
LLM Judges	Claude Opus 4.6 (Judge A) + GPT-4o (Judge B)
Evaluation method	LLM-as-Judge with conservative consensus + human validation on stratified subsample

Each API call follows an identical procedure: construct the prompt by combining the framework template with the case data; send the request with fixed parameters; record the complete response including metadata (response time, token count, timestamp); after all runs are completed, evaluate responses using the LLM-as-Judge protocol. The three runs per configuration are executed sequentially with a minimum 5-second delay between calls to avoid cache or throttling effects. Execution achieved 2,159 successful responses out of 2,160 calls (99.95% completion rate). The generation phase cost US\$ 11.70; the complete experiment including dual-judge evaluation cost US\$ 34.48.

Two protocol design decisions warrant explicit mention. All prompts were sent as **user**-type messages. No framework used the API’s **system** field, which establishes a hierarchy between system instructions and user input. This decision ensures experimental parity: all frameworks receive identical treatment with no architectural advantage for any, but implies that frameworks

natively designed as system prompts (such as ACTFIT) were not tested in their typical deployment configuration. Use of the `system` field is analyzed as a future direction (Section 5.7).

No external tools were made available to the models during the experiment (web search, code execution, calculator, MCPs/external APIs). Models operated exclusively with the information contained in the prompt and their intrinsic pre-trained capabilities. This decision isolates the effect of the prompt framework on the model’s base capability and reflects the most restrictive deployment scenario, common at regulated financial institutions for compliance, security, and auditability reasons. Unlike benchmarks such as HLE and ARC-AGI, which permit or encourage tool use, our benchmark evaluates intrinsic capability governed exclusively by the prompt.

3.8 Experimental Design Limitations

We preemptively acknowledge several limitations.

Simulated dataset. Cases are simulated rather than extracted from real-world applications. This limits ecological validity but guarantees full control over the ground truth. Human validation revealed that the investment ground truth has its own limitations: specifically, some ground truths introduce inferred monetary values not explicitly present in the input profiles (Section 5.5).

Prompt length asymmetry. The ACTFIT template contains ~ 558 words (insurance) and ~ 682 words (investments), a ratio $\sim 2.7\times$ larger than CRISPE and $\sim 15\times$ larger than the baseline. Superior performance may be partially attributable to prompt length rather than structure alone. This confounding limitation is addressed in proposed future work via a prompt-length-normalized experiment (Section 5.7).

Uniform temperature. Temperature 0.3 is applied equally to all three models without cross-calibration. Each model may respond differently to the same temperature value.

LLM-as-Judge with documented bias. The two LLM judges show near-perfect agreement for accuracy ($\kappa = 0.97$) but poor agreement for hallucination ($\kappa = 0.19$). Human validation identified Judge A (Claude Opus 4.6) as substantially more calibrated than Judge B (GPT-4o) for hallucination detection (κ human-Judge A = 0.82 vs. κ human-Judge B = -0.54). The conservative consensus protocol partially mitigates this problem by adopting the more severe score in disagreements, but hallucination results should be interpreted with caution (Section 4.5).

Prompts as user messages. As noted, all frameworks were sent as `user`-type messages without using the API’s `system` field. Anthropic’s and OpenAI’s documentation indicates that system prompts receive differentiated treatment in response generation, although implementation details are not public. Frameworks designed for primary use as system prompts (such as ACTFIT) may perform differently when deployed in their native configuration, meaning the results reported here may underestimate ACTFIT performance under real-world agentic deployment conditions.

No external tools. Models operated without access to web search, code execution, or external tools via APIs/MCPs. In real-world deployment, models frequently have tool access that can improve accuracy and reduce hallucination.

Single human evaluator. Human validation was conducted by the author, introducing potential bias. External validation by independent evaluators is planned as an extension.

Commercial models only. Results may not generalize to open-source alternatives.

Two tasks in one domain. Both tasks belong to the financial domain. Generalization to other regulated domains requires further study.

Point-in-time snapshot. LLMs are updated frequently. Our results reflect model behavior at the testing date (February 2026). We report exact version identifiers to enable replication.

4. Results

Results presented in this section use scores consolidated by the conservative consensus protocol between two independent LLM judges (Claude Opus 4.6 and GPT-4o), validated by human evaluation on a stratified subsample (n=98). Inter-rater agreement, human-machine calibration, bias analysis, and cost analysis are reported in Sections 4.5-4.7.

4.1 Aggregate Performance by Framework

Table 5 presents aggregate performance across all models, tasks, and complexity levels.

Table 5. Aggregate performance by framework ($N = 2,158$, conservative consensus).

Framework	N	Accuracy	Hallucination	Consistency	Eff. Score
Baseline (zero-shot)	539	44.9%	23.2%	93.9%	0.342
Few-shot (2 examples)	540	61.3%	7.2%	86.1%	0.492
CRISPE	540	41.1%	49.1%	91.7%	0.253
ACTFIT	539	67.0%	15.8%	92.8%	0.537

Note: N = number of evaluated responses (from 2,160 calls, 2,158 yielded valid evaluation from both judges). Scores by conservative consensus: agreement \rightarrow consensus score; disagreement \rightarrow acc = min, hal = max. Efficiency Score = $(Accuracy \times Consistency) / (1 + Hallucination)$. Consistency = proportion of cases with identical results across 3 independent runs.

ACTFIT achieves the highest accuracy (67.0%) and the highest Efficiency Score (0.537), exceeding the baseline by +22.1 percentage points in accuracy and +56.8% in Efficiency Score. Few-shot ranks second in accuracy (61.3%) and exhibits the lowest hallucination rate in the experiment (7.2%). Figure 1 visualizes this contrast between accuracy and hallucination across the four frameworks.

The most striking result is CRISPE: it not only shows the worst accuracy among all frameworks (41.1%, below the baseline itself) but also the highest hallucination rate (49.1%) — nearly half of all responses contain fabricated information. CRISPE’s Efficiency Score (0.253) is 26% below the baseline (0.342). More structure does not necessarily mean better performance. This inversion is one of the central findings of this study.

Consistency (proportion of cases where all three independent runs produced identical results) is high across all frameworks (86.1%-93.9%), indicating that models are relatively stable in their responses regardless of the structure received. The slight consistency reduction for Few-shot (86.1%) may indicate that examples introduce additional variability by expanding the space of acceptable responses.

Figure 1. Accuracy and hallucination rate by framework (aggregate across all models and tasks). ACTFIT achieves the highest accuracy (67.0%) while CRISPE produces the highest hallucination rate (49.1%). Few-shot achieves the lowest hallucination (7.2%). Conservative consensus scores, $N = 2,158$.

4.2 Framework × Task Interaction

Table 6 disaggregates performance by task, revealing a significant interaction between framework and task type. Figure 2 presents this asymmetry as a dual panel, making the contrast between insurance and investment scenarios visually immediate.

Figure 2. Performance by task: insurance (left) vs. investment (right). The governance effect is task-dependent: insurance shows modest differentiation (baseline already at 74.4%), while investment reveals dramatic separation (ACTFIT at 61.7% vs. baseline at 15.6%). Conservative consensus scores.

Note: Conservative consensus between Judge A (Claude Opus 4.6) and Judge B (GPT-4o). N per cell = ~ 270 (3 models \times 30 cases \times 3 runs). Investment accuracy uses $\pm 5pp$ tolerance per asset class.

The asymmetry between tasks is the most dramatic finding in the dataset. In insurance (an essentially categorical task with relatively clear decision boundaries) the baseline already achieves 74.4% accuracy with only 5.6% hallucination, and incremental gains are modest. Few-shot leads

Table 6. Performance by framework and task (conservative consensus).

Framework	Task	N	Accuracy	Hallucination	Consistency	Eff. Score
Baseline	Insurance	269	74.4%	5.6%	92.2%	0.650
Baseline	Investments	270	15.6%	40.7%	95.6%	0.106
Few-shot	Insurance	270	79.3%	1.5%	88.9%	0.694
Few-shot	Investments	270	43.3%	13.0%	83.3%	0.320
CRISPE	Insurance	270	64.4%	21.9%	88.9%	0.470
CRISPE	Investments	270	17.8%	76.3%	94.4%	0.095
ACTFIT	Insurance	270	72.2%	12.2%	94.4%	0.608
ACTFIT	Investments	269	61.7%	19.3%	91.1%	0.471

marginally (79.3%). ACTFIT matches the baseline (72.2%) without surpassing it on this task, while CRISPE degrades performance to 64.4%.

In investments (a task involving numerical reasoning, multiple criteria, and trade-offs between time horizon and risk profile) the picture reverses entirely. The baseline collapses to 15.6% accuracy with 40.7% hallucination. ACTFIT rises to 61.7% (+46.1pp over the baseline), reducing hallucination to 19.3%. ACTFIT’s Efficiency Score on investments (0.471) is 4.5× the baseline (0.106). This is the largest absolute delta in the dataset and constitutes the principal finding of this study.

CRISPE shows a particularly negative result on investments: 17.8% accuracy (barely above the baseline) combined with 76.3% hallucination — over three-quarters of responses contain fabricated information. The Efficiency Score of 0.095 is the lowest in the entire dataset. The hypothesis is that CRISPE’s “Personality” component encourages the model to “get into character” and produce persuasive responses, fabricating data as needed to sound convincing. This finding suggests that poorly designed governance can be actively counterproductive, degrading both accuracy and factual integrity.

The pattern is consistent with the interpretation that structured governance has an effect proportional to task complexity: when the task is simple enough for the model to solve without guidance, additional governance contributes marginally; when the task exceeds the model’s unguided capability, governance functions as institutional infrastructure that compensates for the deficit.

4.3 Framework × Model Interaction

Table 7 presents performance disaggregated by framework and model, revealing a strong interaction between prompt structure and base model capability. Figure 3 visualizes this interaction as an Efficiency Score heatmap by framework × model, where the GPT-4.1 + ACTFIT peak (E = 0.789) contrasts visually with the Gemini 2.5 Flash + CRISPE trough (E = 0.126).

Note: N per cell = ~180 (2 tasks × 30 cases × 3 runs). Conservative consensus. Bold indicates dataset peak.

The three models exhibit distinct profiles under baseline conditions. Claude Sonnet 4.5 is the most “assertive”: highest accuracy without a framework (57.2%) but also the highest hallucination rate (27.8%). GPT-4.1 occupies an intermediate, balanced position (39.1% accuracy,

Figure 3. Efficiency Score heatmap by framework and model. Each cell shows the composite Efficiency Score $E = (A \times C)/(1 + H)$. The GPT-4.1 + ACTFIT peak ($E = 0.789$) contrasts with the Gemini 2.5 Flash + CRISPE trough ($E = 0.126$). Conservative consensus scores.

Table 7. Performance by framework and model (conservative consensus).

Framework	Model	N	Accuracy	Hallucination	Consistency	Eff. Score
Baseline	Claude S4.5	180	57.2%	27.8%	98.3%	0.440
Baseline	GPT-4.1	179	39.1%	10.6%	95.0%	0.336
Baseline	Gemini 2.5F	180	38.3%	31.1%	88.3%	0.258
Few-shot	Claude S4.5	180	70.0%	8.9%	100.0%	0.643
Few-shot	GPT-4.1	180	60.0%	7.2%	81.7%	0.457
Few-shot	Gemini 2.5F	180	53.9%	5.6%	76.7%	0.391
CRISPE	Claude S4.5	180	55.0%	61.1%	95.0%	0.324
CRISPE	GPT-4.1	180	45.0%	25.0%	93.3%	0.336
CRISPE	Gemini 2.5F	180	23.3%	61.1%	86.7%	0.126
ACTFIT	Claude S4.5	180	73.9%	18.9%	98.3%	0.611
ACTFIT	GPT-4.1	180	81.7%	0.0%	96.7%	0.789
ACTFIT	Gemini 2.5F	179	45.2%	28.5%	83.3%	0.294

10.6% hallucination). Gemini 2.5 Flash is the most volatile: weakest baseline (38.3%) with high hallucination (31.1%) and lowest consistency (88.3%).

The central finding in Table 7 is the framework \times model interaction. The ACTFIT vs. baseline delta varies substantially (Figure 4):

Figure 4. ACTFIT vs. Baseline accuracy delta by model. GPT-4.1 benefits most from structured governance (+42.6pp), inverting the model hierarchy established under baseline conditions. Error represents the absolute accuracy gain in percentage points.

Model	Baseline Acc.	ACTFIT Acc.	Δ ACTFIT vs. Baseline
GPT-4.1	39.1%	81.7%	+42.6pp
Claude S4.5	57.2%	73.9%	+16.7pp
Gemini 2.5F	38.3%	45.2%	+6.9pp

GPT-4.1 benefits most from ACTFIT, with a 42.6 percentage point jump, and simultaneously achieves 0% hallucination under ACTFIT — the only zero-hallucination case in the entire dataset. Its Efficiency Score of 0.789 is the absolute peak of the experiment. This result inverts the model hierarchy: under baseline, GPT-4.1 ranks second; under ACTFIT, it leads by a wide margin.

Claude Sonnet 4.5 starts from a higher baseline and obtains a moderate gain (+16.7pp), but its hallucination rate remains elevated (18.9%) even under ACTFIT, suggesting that governance reduces but does not eliminate the model’s tendency toward fabrication. Gemini 2.5 Flash responds weakly to ACTFIT (+6.9pp), maintaining high hallucination (28.5%) and low consistency (83.3%).

CRISPE produces a heterogeneous effect across models: it degrades Claude Sonnet 4.5 from 27.8% to 61.1% hallucination (+33.3pp) and produces the same effect on Gemini 2.5 Flash (31.1% → 61.1%). GPT-4.1 is more resistant to CRISPE’s damage (hallucination rises from 10.6% to 25.0%), possibly due to greater intrinsic robustness to persona instructions.

These patterns suggest that structured governance is a *complement* to base model capability: models with higher “receptiveness” to structure (GPT-4.1) are unlocked by it, while models with lower receptiveness (Gemini 2.5 Flash) capture only marginal benefits. The direction of the effect (positive for restriction-oriented governance, negative for persona-oriented governance) is consistent across all models.

4.4 Complexity and Consistency

Table 8 disaggregates performance by complexity level, testing the hypothesis that the governance effect is difficulty-dependent.

Table 8. Performance by framework and complexity (conservative consensus).

Framework	Complexity	N	Accuracy	Hallucination	Consistency	Eff. Score
Baseline	Simple	179	47.5%	19.0%	96.7%	0.386
Baseline	Medium	216	49.5%	26.4%	93.1%	0.365
Baseline	Difficult	144	34.7%	23.6%	91.7%	0.258
Few-shot	Simple	180	80.0%	3.9%	90.0%	0.693
Few-shot	Medium	216	53.2%	8.8%	84.7%	0.415
Few-shot	Difficult	144	50.0%	9.0%	83.3%	0.382
CRISPE	Simple	180	46.7%	38.9%	95.0%	0.319
CRISPE	Medium	216	45.8%	53.2%	93.1%	0.278
CRISPE	Difficult	144	27.1%	55.6%	85.4%	0.149
ACTFIT	Simple	180	87.2%	11.7%	91.7%	0.716
ACTFIT	Medium	215	60.5%	17.2%	94.4%	0.487
ACTFIT	Difficult	144	51.4%	18.8%	91.7%	0.397

Note: N varies by complexity (Simple: 10 cases × 3 models × 3 runs × 2 tasks = 180; Medium: 216; Difficult: 144). Conservative consensus.

Performance degrades monotonically with complexity for all frameworks, as expected. The degradation rate, however, varies across frameworks, revealing an informative pattern. Figure 5 visualizes the degradation curves of the four frameworks, making it evident that ACTFIT degrades more slowly than the alternatives.

Figure 5. Accuracy degradation by complexity level for each framework. All frameworks degrade monotonically with complexity. ACTFIT degrades more slowly than alternatives and is the only framework maintaining accuracy above 50% on difficult cases (51.4%). Conservative consensus scores.

The ACTFIT vs. baseline delta widens with complexity:

ACTFIT produces the largest absolute gain on simple cases (+39.7pp), raising accuracy from 47.5% to 87.2%. On difficult cases, the gain is smaller in absolute terms (+16.7pp) but ACTFIT

Complexity	Baseline Acc.	ACTFIT Acc.	Δ	Baseline E	ACTFIT E	ΔE
Simple	47.5%	87.2%	+39.7pp	0.386	0.716	+85.5%
Medium	49.5%	60.5%	+11.0pp	0.365	0.487	+33.4%
Difficult	34.7%	51.4%	+16.7pp	0.258	0.397	+53.9%

is the only framework that maintains accuracy above 50% (51.4% vs. 34.7% for the baseline and 27.1% for CRISPE). ACTFIT’s Efficiency Score on difficult cases (0.397) is 53.9% above the baseline (0.258) and $2.7\times$ CRISPE’s (0.149).

Few-shot exhibits a notable pattern: it is especially effective on simple cases (80.0%) but the advantage compresses on medium and difficult cases (53.2% and 50.0%), converging with ACTFIT. This suggests that examples are sufficient to guide responses in scenarios that resemble the provided examples but insufficient when complexity demands generalizable reasoning beyond those examples.

CRISPE’s hallucination rate scales alarmingly with complexity: 38.9% (simple) \rightarrow 53.2% (medium) \rightarrow 55.6% (difficult). ACTFIT, by contrast, keeps hallucination relatively contained: 11.7% \rightarrow 17.2% \rightarrow 18.8%. Restriction-oriented governance demonstrates the ability to contain fabrication even under complexity pressure, while persona-oriented governance amplifies the tendency toward fabrication when the model faces uncertainty.

Consistency. The consistency pattern is less differentiated across frameworks. All maintain high consistency (83.3%-98.3%), with modest degradation as complexity increases. ACTFIT shows stable consistency (91.7% on both simple and difficult, 94.4% on medium), while Few-shot shows the largest variation (90.0% \rightarrow 84.7% \rightarrow 83.3%). The interpretation is that ACTFIT governance stabilizes not just response quality but also reproducibility.

4.5 Inter-Rater Agreement and Human Validation

This subsection reports evaluation protocol results at three levels: agreement between the two LLM judges, agreement between each judge and the human evaluator, and implications for interpreting the consolidated scores.

4.5.1 Inter-Judge Agreement

Table 9 presents agreement between Judge A (Claude Opus 4.6) and Judge B (GPT-4o) for the two evaluated dimensions.

Table 9. Inter-judge agreement ($N = 2,158$).

Dimension	Raw Agreement	Cohen’s κ	Interpretation (Landis & Koch)
Accuracy	2,126/2,158 (98.5%)	0.970	Almost Perfect
Hallucination	1,737/2,158 (80.5%)	0.194	Poor

Note: Cohen’s κ calculated over $N=2,158$ paired evaluations. Interpretation follows Landis and Koch (1977).

Agreement on accuracy is near-perfect: the two judges disagree on only 32 of 2,158 evaluations. For practical purposes, accuracy as reported in this study is essentially agnostic to judge selection.

Agreement on hallucination is substantially lower. Although raw agreement is 80.5%, Cohen’s κ is only 0.194, indicating that observed agreement barely exceeds chance. The discrepancy between high raw agreement and low κ stems from asymmetric marginal distributions: both judges agree that most responses are *not* hallucinated, inflating raw agreement, yet they diverge systematically on *which* responses are hallucinated. The 421 disagreement cases distribute asymmetrically across models (Section 4.6), suggesting systematic bias rather than random noise.

4.5.2 Human-Machine Agreement

Human validation (n=98 cases, including 42 hallucination disagreements from Block 3) enabled calibrating each LLM judge against human judgment. Table 10 presents the results.

Table 10. Human-machine agreement by dimension and judge.

Dimension	Metric	Human × Judge A (Claude)	Human × Judge B (GPT-4o)
Hallucination (Block 3, n=42)	Raw agreement	92.9%	7.1%
	Cohen’s κ	0.82 (Almost Perfect)	-0.54 (worse than chance)
Accuracy (all blocks, n=98)	Raw agreement	90.8%	76.5%
	Cohen’s κ	0.77 (Substantial)	0.49 (Moderate)

Note: Block 3 (hallucination): n=42 inter-judge disagreement cases, evaluated by 1 human evaluator (the author). Accuracy: n=98 cases across all blocks.

The result is unambiguous. For hallucination detection, Judge A (Claude Opus 4.6) is substantially calibrated with human judgment ($\kappa = 0.82$), while Judge B (GPT-4o) is systematically *inverted* ($\kappa = -0.54$) — its performance is worse than random classification. For accuracy, both judges are reasonable, but Judge A remains superior ($\kappa = 0.77$ vs. 0.49). Figure 6 visualizes this dramatic asymmetry.

Figure 6. Human-machine agreement asymmetry. Judge A (Claude Opus 4.6) achieves $\kappa = 0.82$ (Almost Perfect) with the human evaluator for hallucination detection, while Judge B (GPT-4o) achieves $\kappa = -0.54$ (worse than chance). Human validation on Block 3 (n = 42 inter-judge disagreement cases).

Pattern analysis in Block 3 confirms the direction of disagreement:

Note: Block 3 of human validation (n=42). “A=hal” indicates Judge A flagged hallucination; “B=ok” indicates Judge B did not. Accurate/inaccurate refers to the accuracy consensus.

Table 11. Human validation by disagreement pattern (Block 3, $n = 42$).

Disagreement pattern	Pat- n	Human agrees with A	Human agrees with B
P1: A=hal, B=ok (inaccurate case)	5	60%	40%
P2: A=ok, B=hal (inaccurate case)	5	100%	0%
P3: A=hal, B=ok (accurate case)	7	100%	0%
P4: A=ok, B=hal (accurate case)	25	96%	4%

Patterns P2, P3, and P4 (representing 88% of Block 3) show human agreement with Judge A in 96-100% of cases. P4 is the most frequent pattern (25 cases): Judge B flags as hallucination responses that both the human and Judge A consider free of fabrication. This is the primary driver of Judge B’s negative κ .

Stabilization test. To verify that the pattern is not an artifact of a subsample, we compared the two halves of Block 3: in the first 21 cases, the human agreed with Judge A 90% of the time; in the last 21, 95%. The convergence between halves, with no statistical drift, supported the decision to suspend validation by saturation criterion at case 99.

4.5.3 Implications for Result Interpretation

These findings carry three direct implications. The **accuracy** scores reported in this study are highly reliable (inter-judge $\kappa = 0.97$, human-Judge A $\kappa = 0.77$). The **hallucination** scores consolidated by conservative consensus should be interpreted as conservative estimates (upper bound): by adopting hal = max in disagreements, we incorporate Judge B detections that human validation demonstrated to be predominantly false positives. Judge A (Claude Opus 4.6) is the calibrated reference judge for hallucination; Judge A scores alone are more accurate than consensus scores. We report consensus scores as a conservative baseline, consistent with the cautionary posture appropriate to regulated financial domains.

4.6 Inter-Judge Bias Analysis

Hallucination disagreement is not uniformly distributed across models. Table 12 presents the hallucination rate attributed by each judge to each evaluated model.

Table 12. Hallucination rate by model, disaggregated by judge.

Evaluated Model	Judge A (Claude)	Judge B (GPT-4o)	Δ (A – B)	Judge A Family	Judge B Family
Claude Sonnet 4.5	28.5%	6.5%	+21.9pp	Same (Anthropic)	Different
GPT-4.1	10.4%	0.6%	+9.9pp	Different	Same (OpenAI)
Gemini 2.5 Flash	7.4%	31.0%	−23.6pp	Different	Different

Note: Hallucination rates calculated individually by judge (pre-consensus). “Same” indicates the judge belongs to the same model family as the evaluated model.

The pattern is anti-family, not pro-family: each judge is *more severe* with its own family’s model. Judge A (Claude) attributes 28.5% hallucination to Claude Sonnet 4.5 — nearly 4× the

6.5% attributed by Judge B. Symmetrically, Judge B (GPT-4o) is lenient with GPT-4.1 (0.6% hallucination) while Judge A attributes 10.4%. Figure 7 visualizes this anti-family pattern.

Figure 7. Anti-family bias in hallucination detection. Each judge is more severe with its own family’s model: Judge A (Claude) attributes 28.5% hallucination to Claude Sonnet 4.5, while Judge B (GPT-4o) attributes only 6.5%. The pattern reverses for Gemini 2.5 Flash. Hallucination rates disaggregated by judge (pre-consensus).

The most extreme case is Gemini 2.5 Flash, which has no same-family judge: Judge A attributes only 7.4% hallucination, while Judge B attributes 31.0% — a 23.6 percentage point difference. This suggests Judge B’s bias extends beyond the intra-family relationship.

Table 13 details hallucination disagreement patterns by model.

Table 13. Hallucination disagreement patterns by evaluated model ($N = 2,158$).

Evaluated Model	N	Both = 0	Both = 1	Only A = 1	Only B = 1
Claude Sonnet 4.5	720	510 (70.8%)	42 (5.8%)	163 (22.6%)	5 (0.7%)
GPT-4.1	719	642 (89.3%)	2 (0.3%)	73 (10.2%)	2 (0.3%)
Gemini 2.5 Flash	719	492 (68.4%)	49 (6.8%)	4 (0.6%)	174 (24.2%)

Note: “Both = 0” = neither judge detected hallucination; “Both = 1” = both detected; “Only A = 1” = only Judge A detected; “Only B = 1” = only Judge B detected.

The pattern is asymmetric and mirrored. For Claude Sonnet 4.5, 22.6% of evaluations have hallucination detected *only* by Judge A (Claude), with only 0.7% detected only by Judge B. For Gemini 2.5 Flash, the situation inverts: 24.2% detected only by Judge B, with only 0.6% detected only by Judge A. GPT-4.1 presents the cleanest profile: 89.3% agreement on non-hallucination, with residual disagreement concentrated in Judge A (10.2%).

Given that human validation calibrated Judge A as the reference ($\kappa = 0.82$), the most parsimonious interpretation is: Judge A is detecting real hallucinations in Claude Sonnet 4.5 (legitimate severity toward the “sibling”), while Judge B is generating massive false positives for Gemini 2.5 Flash (unjustified severity). Accuracy, by contrast, is consistent between judges ($\Delta < 2pp$ for all models), confirming that bias is specific to the hallucination dimension.

This finding contributes to the emerging literature on LLM-as-Judge bias: bias can operate in the *opposite* direction from expected (anti-family rather than pro-family) and can be asymmetric across dimensions (strong in hallucination, absent in accuracy).

Recent studies have documented multiple forms of bias in LLM evaluators. Wataoka et al. (2024) introduced a quantitative metric for self-preference bias, demonstrating that GPT-4 exhibits significant self-preference: the LLM tends to evaluate more favorably outputs that are more familiar to it, as measured by lower perplexity. Ye et al. (2024) conducted a systematic analysis of LLM-as-Judge biases, including positional, verbosity, and self-enhancement biases. Our finding of *anti-family* bias (where each judge is more severe with its own family’s models) complements this literature by demonstrating that bias direction is not universally self-favoring. One explanatory hypothesis is that models trained with RLHF develop greater sensitivity to their own family’s error patterns through familiarity with typical failure modes. This hypothesis is consistent with Wataoka et al.’s (2024) observation that familiarity (perplexity) is the mechanism underlying self-preference bias; in our case, however, familiarity operates in the opposite direction: recognition of flaws rather than preference for style.

4.7 Cost Analysis

Table 14 presents the cost per API call, cost per correct response, and efficiency metrics for each framework, using official API prices as of February 2026. Figure 8 visualizes the relationship between cost and accuracy for all 24 configurations, where dot size reflects the non-hallucination rate ($1 - \text{hallucination rate}$).

Figure 8. Cost per API call vs. accuracy for all 24 configurations (4 frameworks \times 3 models \times 2 tasks). Dot size reflects the non-hallucination rate ($1 - H$). The upper-left quadrant (high accuracy, low cost) is dominated by ACTFIT and Few-shot configurations. Data from Table 14.

Note: Costs calculated with official API prices as of Feb/2026. Cost/Correct = Average cost per call / Accuracy. Accuracy and hallucination metrics by conservative consensus.

Table 14. Cost and efficiency by framework (aggregated across models and tasks).

Framework	N	Avg Cost/Call	Accuracy	Hallucination	Eff. Score	Cost/Correct
Baseline	539	US\$ 0.0042	44.9%	23.2%	0.342	US\$ 0.0093
Few-shot	540	US\$ 0.0040	61.3%	7.2%	0.492	US\$ 0.0065
CRISPE	540	US\$ 0.0076	41.1%	49.1%	0.253	US\$ 0.0186
ACTFIT	539	US\$ 0.0059	67.0%	15.8%	0.537	US\$ 0.0088

ACTFIT costs 41% more per call than the baseline (US\$ 0.0059 vs. US\$ 0.0042), reflecting the 5.5× longer prompt. When normalized by correct responses, however, ACTFIT (US\$ 0.0088/correct) is only 5% less efficient than Few-shot (US\$ 0.0065/correct), and both are substantially superior to the baseline (US\$ 0.0093/correct) and CRISPE (US\$ 0.0186/correct). CRISPE is the most expensive on both metrics: higher cost per call (long prompts with verbose outputs) *and* lower correct response rate, yielding a cost/correct 2× higher than ACTFIT.

4.7.1 Cost × Model × Framework Interaction

The most deployment-relevant finding emerges when cost analysis is disaggregated by model and task. Table 15 presents the five most cost-efficient configurations for the investment task, the task where prompt governance shows the greatest impact.

Table 15. Top 5 configurations by cost-efficiency in investments (cost/correct).

#	Framework	Model	Cost/Call	Accuracy	Hallucination	Eff. Score	Cost/Correct
1	Few-shot	Gemini 2.5F	US\$ 0.0004	34.4%	8.9%	0.211	US\$ 0.0012
2	ACTFIT	Gemini 2.5F	US\$ 0.0007	33.7%	29.2%	0.200	US\$ 0.0021
3	ACTFIT	GPT-4.1	US\$ 0.0048	80.0%	0.0%	0.800	US\$ 0.0060
4	Few-shot	GPT-4.1	US\$ 0.0056	42.2%	12.2%	0.314	US\$ 0.0132
5	Few-shot	Claude S4.5	US\$ 0.0085	53.3%	17.8%	0.453	US\$ 0.0159

Note: Investment task only. Cost/Correct = Cost/Call ÷ Accuracy. Configuration #3 (bold) recommended for high-reliability deployment.

Configuration #1 (Few-shot + Gemini) is the cheapest per correct response (US\$ 0.0012) but gets only one-third right — inadequate where reliability matters. Configuration #3 (**ACTFIT** + **GPT-4.1**) is the most relevant for real-world deployment: 80% accuracy, zero hallucination, and an Efficiency Score of 0.800 at US\$ 0.006 per correct response. Compared with the more intuitive alternative (Claude Sonnet 4.5 + ACTFIT): GPT-4.1 is 2.9× cheaper per call, 9pp more accurate, and eliminates hallucinations entirely.

For insurance, the simpler task, the pattern favors cheap models: Gemini 2.5 Flash + Baseline achieves 75.6% accuracy at US\$ 0.0005/correct. But the peak quality configuration remains GPT-4.1 + ACTFIT: 83.3% accuracy with 0% hallucination at US\$ 0.0056/correct.

4.7.2 Total Experiment Cost

The total cost of the experiment was **US\$ 34.48**, distributed across two phases. The generation phase (2,158 productive API calls) cost US\$ 11.70, distributed highly asymmetrically across models: Claude Sonnet 4.5 accounted for 67% of generation cost (US\$ 7.89), GPT-4.1 for 30% (US\$ 3.50), and Gemini 2.5 Flash for 3% (US\$ 0.31). The evaluation phase (2 × 2,158 judge calls)

cost US\$ 22.78: Judge A (Claude Opus 4.6) accounted for US\$ 16.58 and Judge B (GPT-4o) for US\$ 6.20. Notably, Judge A alone cost 2.1× more than the entire generation phase, a reminder that rigorous multi-judge evaluation is not free, even when the generation itself is inexpensive. This pricing asymmetry reinforces the finding that cheaper models can be not merely competitive but superior when combined with appropriate structured governance.

4.7.3 CRISPE as Cost Penalty

CRISPE exhibits the worst cost-efficiency profile in the dataset. On investments, Claude Sonnet 4.5 + CRISPE costs US\$ 0.0209 per call with 31.1% accuracy and 90.0% hallucination, yielding US\$ 0.0671 per correct response — **11× more expensive** than GPT-4.1 + ACTFIT (US\$ 0.0060/correct) with 2.6× lower accuracy. Gemini 2.5 Flash + CRISPE on investments reaches 0% accuracy with 98.9% hallucination — cost/correct is incalculable (division by zero). Persona-oriented governance not only degrades quality: it amplifies operational costs by generating long, verbose, and factually incorrect outputs.

4.8 Statistical Significance of Main Comparisons

To assess the robustness of the findings, we apply Fisher’s exact test to between-framework comparisons for accuracy and hallucination, with 95% confidence intervals for the deltas. Table 16 reports the results.

Table 16. Statistical significance of between-framework comparisons (Fisher’s exact test, 95% CI).

Comparison	Metric	Δ (pp)	95% CI	χ^2	p (Fisher)	Sig.
ACTFIT vs. Baseline	Accuracy	+22.1	[16.3; 27.9]	52.40	3.6×10^{-13}	***
ACTFIT vs. Baseline	Hallucination	-7.4	[-12.1; -2.7]	9.00	2.7×10^{-3}	**
ACTFIT vs. CRISPE	Accuracy	+25.9	[20.1; 31.6]	71.62	1.4×10^{-17}	***
ACTFIT vs. CRISPE	Hallucination	-33.3	[-38.5; -28.1]	135.01	2.3×10^{-32}	***
ACTFIT vs. Few-shot	Accuracy	+5.7	[-0.0; 11.4]	3.54	5.7×10^{-2}	ns
ACTFIT vs. Few-shot	Hallucination	+8.5	[4.8; 12.3]	18.55	9.9×10^{-6}	***
Few-shot vs. Baseline	Accuracy	+16.4	[10.5; 22.3]	28.47	7.6×10^{-8}	***
Few-shot vs. Baseline	Hallucination	-16.0	[-20.1; -11.8]	52.14	1.1×10^{-13}	***

Note: *** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$; ns = not significant. Two-tailed Fisher’s exact test on 2×2 contingency tables. CIs calculated by normal approximation for difference of proportions. N per framework: 539–540 observations.

ACTFIT’s superiority over the baseline and CRISPE is highly significant for both metrics ($p < 0.001$). The ACTFIT vs. Few-shot comparison reveals an important nuance: the accuracy gain (+5.7pp) is **not** statistically significant ($p = 0.057$), and ACTFIT shows a significantly *higher* hallucination rate than Few-shot (+8.5pp, $p < 0.001$). This finding qualifies the narrative: ACTFIT outperforms Few-shot on Efficiency Score (0.537 vs. 0.492) through superior consistency and better performance on complex tasks, but does not outperform it in a statistically robust manner on pure accuracy when data are aggregated. Task-level disaggregation (Table 6) reveals that ACTFIT’s gain concentrates on investments (+18.4pp), where task complexity justifies the additional governance.

5. Discussion

5.1 The Governance Effect: Why Structure Matters

Our results reveal a consistent pattern we term the *governance effect*: the relative performance of frameworks is *dependent on task complexity*. In simple or categorical tasks (insurance), structured governance offers marginal gains because the baseline already performs adequately when the task itself provides sufficient structure. In ambiguous tasks involving trade-offs (investments), structured governance produces dramatic gains: up to 46.1 percentage points for ACTFIT vs. baseline. This pattern is consistent with three complementary hypotheses about the underlying mechanism.

Ambiguity reduction. ACTFIT explicitly specifies what the model must produce (Format), how it should reason (Task with numbered process), and what constitutes an adequate response (Illustration). In ambiguous tasks, this specification reduces the model’s decision space, channeling inference toward the subset of acceptable responses. The empirical evidence is direct: in investments, where the space of possible responses is vast (infinite combinations of percentages), ACTFIT reduces hallucination from 40.7% (baseline) to 19.3%, a 52.6% reduction.

Fabrication prevention. ACTFIT’s Tone component includes explicit anti-hallucination instructions (“rely exclusively on the provided data,” “do not fabricate information”). When the model encounters uncertainty in complex tasks, these instructions function as constraints that prevent opportunistic data fabrication. GPT-4.1 under ACTFIT achieves 0% hallucination across 180 responses, evidence that for at least some models, governance can completely eliminate factual fabrication.

Output discipline. The Format component provides an explicit response template. This eliminates the step where the model decides *how* to organize the output, reducing tokens spent on structuring and focusing computational capacity on response *substance*. Cost data (Section 4.7) support this hypothesis: ACTFIT generates shorter responses than the baseline on investments (288 tokens vs. 699 tokens for GPT-4.1), despite receiving longer prompts. The prompt structure *is* cognitive infrastructure that reduces the model’s informational transaction costs — the computational and probabilistic cost of selecting, organizing, and verifying relevant information in the absence of structural constraints.

This interpretation positions structured prompts not as technical optimization but as *institutional design* — a governance layer at the interface between raw model capability and the domain-specific task. This connection between prompt engineering and institutional theory is explored in greater depth in the second paper of this series (Girolli, 2026, in preparation).

This governance effect encounters an apparent tension with Anh-Hoang et al. (2025), who reported that hallucination rate is weakly perturbed by prompting technique, being dominated by intrinsic model variability. In their study, alternating between zero-shot, few-shot, CoT, instruction, and vague prompting produced minimal hallucination rate variation: the model hallucinated at similar rates regardless of technique. Our data show the opposite: ACTFIT reduces hallucination from 23.2% (baseline) to 15.8% ($\Delta = -7.4\text{pp}$, $p = 0.003$), and the reduction is even more dramatic in specific configurations (GPT-4.1: from 10.6% to 0.0%).

The reconciliation lies in the granularity of specification. The five techniques tested by Anh-Hoang et al. (zero-shot, few-shot, CoT, generic instruction, vague prompt) vary in the *amount*

of information provided to the model but not in the *type* of behavioral constraint imposed. None of them explicitly defines what the model must not do, how it should format the output, or what consequences data fabrication carries. They are variations of intensity along the same axis. A governance framework like ACTFIT operates on a different axis entirely: it defines qualitative constraints (explicit anti-hallucination directives), structural constraints (output template eliminating space for fabrication), and contextual constraints (regulated domain specification). The implication is that perturbing the hallucination rate requires institutional specification, not merely instructional specification, a distinction our data make empirically operationalizable and that Anh-Hoang et al.’s data corroborate by exclusion.

5.2 Framework \times Model Interaction: Governance as Capability Unlock

The most unexpected finding in this study is the hierarchy inversion among models under structured governance. Under baseline, GPT-4.1 (39.1%) is inferior to Claude Sonnet 4.5 (57.2%). Under ACTFIT, GPT-4.1 (81.7%) surpasses Claude Sonnet 4.5 (73.9%) and reaches the dataset’s absolute peak with zero hallucination. GPT-4.1’s delta with ACTFIT (+42.6pp) is $2.5\times$ Claude Sonnet 4.5’s (+16.7pp) and $6.2\times$ Gemini 2.5 Flash’s (+6.9pp).

This pattern suggests that models possess different degrees of *governance receptiveness*, a property not captured by traditional benchmarks that evaluate models only under baseline conditions or with standardized prompts. A model with a modest baseline but high receptiveness (GPT-4.1) may be a superior choice for deployment under structured governance, compared to a model with a high baseline but low receptiveness (Claude Sonnet 4.5).

The practical implication is substantial. Conventional model evaluation (selecting the model with the best benchmark under standard conditions) can produce suboptimal decisions for institutions implementing prompt governance. Our data suggest that evaluation should be conducted *jointly*: model \times framework, not model in isolation. For investments, the GPT-4.1 + ACTFIT combination (80% accuracy, 0% hallucination, $E=0.800$) is radically superior to Claude Sonnet 4.5 + ACTFIT (71.1% accuracy, 28.9% hallucination, $E=0.533$), despite Claude Sonnet 4.5 being the model with the best global baseline.

The tentative explanation is that GPT-4.1 has a “disciplined receptiveness” profile: low intrinsic fabrication rate (10.6% baseline, the lowest among the three models) combined with high capacity to follow structured instructions. Claude Sonnet 4.5, by contrast, has an “assertive” profile: high raw accuracy but a persistent fabrication tendency (27.8% baseline \rightarrow 18.9% ACTFIT) that governance reduces but does not eliminate. Gemini 2.5 Flash responds weakly to any framework, suggesting that below a certain threshold of base capability, governance cannot compensate for fundamental deficits.

The convergence of these findings at the unit prompt level with Poetiq AI’s (2025) findings at the multi-call orchestration system level is noteworthy. Both demonstrate that structure in the application layer interacts with base model capability in a non-linear fashion: the largest gains occur when the structure is appropriate to the model’s capability level. This convergence across different levels of abstraction reinforces the thesis that the relationship between structure and capability is a general property of LLM-based systems, not an artifact of a specific configuration.

5.3 The Negative Finding: CRISPE as Counter-Example

CRISPE’s negative result is as informative as ACTFIT’s positive one. CRISPE does not merely fail to improve performance — it actively degrades it: accuracy 3.8pp below the baseline (41.1% vs. 44.9%), hallucination 25.9pp above (49.1% vs. 23.2%), and Efficiency Score 26% lower (0.253 vs. 0.342). On investments, the scenario reaches extreme proportions: 76.3% hallucination (vs. 40.7% baseline) and, in the Gemini 2.5 Flash + CRISPE configuration, 0% accuracy with 98.9% hallucination.

This finding reveals an important distinction between *governance-oriented structure* and *persona-oriented structure*. ACTFIT and CRISPE have comparable prompt lengths in terms of conceptual complexity (both define six components) but differ fundamentally in design philosophy.

ACTFIT constrains model behavior: it defines *what* to produce (Format with explicit template), *how* to reason (Task with numbered process), and *what not to do* (Tone with anti-hallucination constraints). Each component operates as an institutional constraint reducing degrees of freedom.

CRISPE modulates model style: it defines *who to be* (Capacity + Role + Personality) and *what to sound like* (Experiment with style expectation). The “Personality” component (unique to CRISPE among the tested frameworks) instructs the model to adopt a persuasive, engaging persona. In financial tasks, this produces a perverse effect: the model prioritizes sounding convincing over being factually correct, and fabricates data as needed to maintain the persona’s narrative consistency.

The contrast between ACTFIT and CRISPE demonstrates that the volume of structure is a necessary but insufficient condition for improving performance. The *direction* of the structure (behavioral constraint vs. stylistic modulation) determines whether the effect is positive or negative. In regulated domains where data fabrication carries material consequences, restriction-oriented governance is not merely preferable; persona-oriented governance is actively dangerous.

5.4 Cost Implications for Deployment

The cost analysis (Section 4.7) reveals that structured governance does not operate on a simple “more structure → more cost → better result” trade-off. ACTFIT costs 41% more per call than the baseline (US\$ 0.0059 vs. US\$ 0.0042), but when normalized by correct responses, the difference compresses to 5% (US\$ 0.0088 vs. US\$ 0.0093). Few-shot is the most cost-efficient per correct response (US\$ 0.0065), but ACTFIT outperforms on Efficiency Score (0.537 vs. 0.492) through better accuracy and consistency.

The finding with the greatest practical relevance is the cost-benefit inversion across models under ACTFIT. For investments, GPT-4.1 + ACTFIT delivers 80% accuracy with zero hallucination at US\$ 0.006 per correct response. Claude Sonnet 4.5 + ACTFIT delivers 71.1% accuracy with 28.9% hallucination at US\$ 0.019 per correct response. The cheaper model is simultaneously more accurate, more reliable, and $3.2\times$ less expensive per correct answer. This inversion challenges the intuition that more expensive models are necessarily superior. This finding suggests that prompt governance can democratize access to high-quality financial AI by making more affordable models viable.

For insurance, where the task is simpler, the calculus changes. Gemini 2.5 Flash + Baseline achieves 75.6% accuracy at US\$ 0.0005/correct, the cheapest combination in the dataset. The

implication is that task complexity should govern both framework and model selection: simple tasks dispense with both sophisticated governance and expensive models; complex tasks justify the investment in both. This finding is contingent, however, on the current complexity of the tested tasks. In scenarios where insurance classification incorporates multiple products, composite criteria, or decision automation, the effective complexity approaches the threshold where structured governance demonstrated its greatest impact, suggesting that ACTFIT adoption may become progressively justifiable as financial application sophistication increases.

The total cost of the entire experiment (generation, dual-judge evaluation, and all infrastructure) was US\$ 34.48, of which US\$ 11.70 was generation (2,158 API calls) and US\$ 22.78 was evaluation (4,316 judge calls). Even including rigorous multi-judge validation, this cost is less than one hour of GPU time for fine-tuning. For financial institutions (especially smaller ones), this cost-benefit ratio positions prompt governance as not only a technically viable but economically attractive alternative to fine-tuning.

5.5 Sensitivity Analysis: Ground Truth Limitations

Human validation revealed a dataset limitation that merits explicit treatment. During evaluation of the 98 cases, the human evaluator documented detailed notes on each case, including observations about the ground truth. There were 39 cases with notes classified as “Anti-Ground Truth”: observations about limitations or fabrications in the ground truth itself. Of these, 28 refer to the investment task.

The pattern is consistent: the investment ground truth systematically introduces specific monetary values (net worth amounts, goals in reais, current portfolio composition) in cases where the corresponding fields in the original profile are explicitly marked as N/A. For example, multiple ground truths referenced “R\$ 200,000 in net worth” or “R\$ 600,000 for a beach house” when the Amount to Invest and Goal fields were N/A in the investor profile. This practice (inferring absent data to construct the response) is reasonable as a real-world financial planning exercise but creates a methodological problem: models that fabricate the same inferred data (or similar values) are penalized for hallucination when they are in fact reproducing the same type of inference the ground truth performed.

This finding carries three implications. The hallucination rates reported for investments constitute **conservative estimates**: some detected “hallucinations” are models inferring plausible data from incomplete profiles, behavior that would be considered reasonable in real financial consulting but that the evaluation protocol classifies as fabrication because it diverges from the literal input. The differential effect between frameworks is robust despite this limitation: if the ground truth equally penalizes all frameworks for plausible inferences, the relative ranking (ACTFIT > Few-shot > Baseline > CRISPE) is unaffected; what may be inflated is the absolute magnitude of hallucination rates, not the difference between frameworks. Human validation directly corroborates this interpretation: in Block 3 (42 hallucination disagreements), the human evaluator reduced hallucination relative to conservative consensus in 31 of 42 cases (73.8%), without increasing it in any case. In Block 2 (32 accuracy disagreements), the human evaluator raised accuracy in 30 of 32 cases (93.8%). Both patterns point in the same direction: conservative consensus is systematically pessimistic, and the numbers reported in this paper represent the worst-case scenario.

For future work, we recommend revision of the investment ground truth to distinguish between provided and inferred data; a two-layer hallucination protocol distinguishing fabrication of data absent from the input vs. fabrication of data contradictory to the input; and sensitivity analysis with revised ground truth to estimate the impact on absolute hallucination rates.

5.6 Limitations

Beyond the experimental design limitations (Section 3.8) and ground truth limitations (Section 5.5), three analytical limitations deserve emphasis.

Length confounding. ACTFIT has significantly longer prompts than the other frameworks. Although cost data suggest the mechanism is not purely “more tokens = better results” (given that CRISPE, with intermediate length, performs worse than both Few-shot and the baseline) we cannot fully isolate the effect of structure from the effect of length without an additional controlled experiment.

Single human evaluator. Human validation was conducted by the author. Although the saturation criterion and between-halves stability indicate robustness, the absence of independent evaluators limits generalization. Distribution of a blinded form to external evaluators is planned as an extension.

Potential model version interaction. Results reflect the behavior of specific model versions (model strings reported). Model updates may alter both the baseline and governance receptiveness. Longitudinal reproducibility requires periodic benchmark reapplication.

5.7 Future Work

Eight directions emerge naturally from this study.

Length-controlled experiment. Equalizing prompt length across frameworks (expanding the baseline with neutral text to match ACTFIT’s token count) to isolate the effect of structure from the effect of length. This is the most relevant limitation to address in order to strengthen the causal claim.

Component analysis. Isolating each ACTFIT component’s contribution (Agent, Context, Task, Format, Illustration, Tone) via systematic ablation. The hypothesis is that Format and Illustration are the highest-impact components, while Agent and Context contribute marginally in well-defined tasks. A complementary variant would expand the Illustration component (which in the current experiment contains 1 worked example per task) to 2 or more examples, testing whether ACTFIT with Illustration matched to Few-shot in example count captures combined benefits of institutional governance and demonstration-based learning.

Adaptive governance. Our finding that the governance effect is complexity-dependent suggests an operational extension: using ACTFIT as a *meta-framework that generates calibrated prompts*. In this configuration, ACTFIT would function as a meta-template that, via meta-prompting, generates compressed or expanded versions of itself, capable of *adding, reducing, or eliminating* components based on task complexity. A simple insurance case could receive a prompt preserving only Task and Format while dropping Agent, Context, Illustration, and Tone, essentially a “compressed ACTFIT” comparable in length to zero-shot but retaining output discipline. This concept of *proportional governance* is analogous to the institutional subsidiarity principle and

connects the present work to the meta-prompting literature (Suzgun and Kalai, 2024; Zhou et al., 2022b) and adaptive meta-systems (PoetiQ AI, 2025). Beyond addressing the length confounding limitation, this approach would directly test whether selective structure works even with short prompts.

Receptiveness as a metric. The variation in ACTFIT delta across models (+6.9pp to +42.6pp) suggests that “governance receptiveness” is a measurable model property that could constitute an independent benchmark metric, complementary to existing capability benchmarks. Models with high receptiveness would be preferable for deployment under structured governance, given that their performance can be shaped more effectively by the prompt layer, offering organizations greater control over model behavior without fine-tuning.

System prompt vs. user prompt. Our experiment sent all frameworks as **user** messages, ensuring experimental parity. A complementary experiment would test each framework as a **system** prompt, evaluating its ability to govern responses to unstructured user prompts, a scenario reflecting real agentic deployment, where the framework is fixed and user input is variable. Anthropic’s and OpenAI’s documentation indicates that system prompts receive differentiated treatment in response generation, although implementation details are not public. ACTFIT, natively designed as a system prompt for agents, may show different performance in its typical deployment configuration. This test would address a relevant limitation of the present study and provide practical deployment guidance.

External tool interaction. Our benchmark evaluates intrinsic model capability under prompt governance, without external tools (web search, code execution, calculators, or MCPs). The interaction between prompt governance and *tool-augmented generation* (where the model can consult external sources during execution) is a natural extension that may alter both the baseline and the relative effect of frameworks.

Modular skills as governance extension. The ACTFIT architecture is extensible by design: components such as Task and Format can be reinforced by specialized skill modules (*skills*) that add domain expertise without altering the governance structure. The interaction between framework governance and modular skills is a future direction connecting this empirical work to the theoretical interpretation proposed in the second paper of this series. The interaction with Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) processes is particularly relevant: components such as Context and Task can incorporate dynamically retrieved content, combining the framework’s structural governance with the factual grounding of external sources, a configuration that directly addresses the hallucination problem documented in this study.

Cross-domain expansion. Replicating the benchmark in healthcare (medical triage, medication dosing), legal (contractual risk classification), and regulatory (compliance checks). The hypothesis is that the governance effect generalizes to domains where data fabrication carries material consequences, but the degree of the effect varies with the intrinsic structure of the task.

Theoretical framework. This paper demonstrates *that* structured frameworks work and under what conditions. The question of *why* they work (whether prompt structure operates as a form of institutional governance analogous to economic institutions) is the subject of the next paper in this series (Girolli, 2026, in preparation). The empirical evidence presented here (informational transaction cost reduction, complexity-dependent institutional effect, governance as capability

complement) constitutes the empirical foundation upon which the theoretical interpretation will be built.

6. Conclusion

We present the first controlled empirical benchmark of structured prompt frameworks on high-stakes financial tasks. Our results demonstrate that prompt governance is not uniformly beneficial: its effectiveness depends on both the framework’s structure and the task’s complexity. ACTFIT, a framework oriented toward institutional governance, achieves 67.0% accuracy versus 44.9% for the baseline (+22.1pp), with gains of up to 46.1 percentage points over the baseline on investment tasks. The GPT-4.1 + ACTFIT combination reaches the dataset peak: 81.7% accuracy with 0% hallucination at US\$ 0.006 per correct response. CRISPE, oriented toward persona modulation, degrades performance below the baseline with hallucinations in 49.1% of responses — poorly designed governance is actively counterproductive.

The evaluation protocol (two independent LLM judges with conservative consensus, validated by stratified human evaluation) revealed that reported results constitute conservative estimates. Human validation (n=98) demonstrated near-perfect agreement with Judge A ($\kappa = 0.82$ for hallucination) and identified systematic anti-family bias in LLM judges, contributing to the emerging literature on automated evaluation.

These findings carry direct practical implications: financial institutions deploying LLMs via commercial APIs can significantly improve system reliability through structured prompt engineering, without the cost of fine-tuning, retraining, or model modification. The choice of framework matters, though: governance oriented toward restriction (constraining behavior) outperforms governance oriented toward persona (modulating style), particularly in tasks where data fabrication carries material consequences. Model selection also matters in non-intuitive ways: models evaluated jointly with governance can invert the hierarchies established by traditional benchmarks.

The question that remains open — and that motivates the next paper in this series — is *why* governance works. If structured prompts operate as institutions that reduce informational transaction costs, insights from institutional economics and praxeology may provide a theoretical framework for prompt design. This connection between prompt engineering and economic theory is what we intend to investigate next: not as metaphor, but as an empirically grounded research program.

Disclosure

The author is the creator of the ACTFIT framework and founder of Finantor, a personal financial management company with AI. To mitigate potential bias arising from this relationship, all experimental materials (including complete prompts, datasets, source code, raw scores from both LLM judges, and the human validation form) are made publicly available in the replication repository for independent verification. The experimental design was structured with specific controls: use of two LLM judges from different families, conservative consensus protocol, and human validation on a stratified subsample. Results include findings that do not favor ACTFIT

(hallucination rate higher than Few-shot; accuracy advantage over Few-shot not statistically significant) and negative findings about an alternative framework (CRISPE), reported with equal transparency. The experiment received no external funding.

References

- Anh-Hoang, D., Tran, V., and Nguyen, L.-M. (2025). Survey and analysis of hallucinations in large language models: Attribution to prompting strategies or model behavior. *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence*, 8:1622292.
- Araci, D. (2019). FinBERT: Financial sentiment analysis with pre-trained language models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1908.10063*.
- Bang, Y., Ji, Z., Schelten, A., Hartshorn, A., Fowler, T., Zhang, C., Cancedda, N., and Fung, P. (2025). HalluLens: LLM hallucination benchmark. In *Proceedings of the 63rd Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers)*, pages 24128–24156. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Brown, T. B., Mann, B., Ryder, N., Subbiah, M., Kaplan, J., Dhariwal, P., Neelakantan, A., Shyam, P., Sastry, G., Askell, A., et al. (2020). Language models are few-shot learners. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 33:1877–1901.
- Elnashar, A., White, J., and Schmidt, D. C. (2025). Prompt engineering for structured data: A comparative evaluation of styles and LLM performance. *Artificial Intelligence and Autonomous Systems*, 2025(2):0009.
- Fernando, C., Banarse, D., Michalewski, H., Osindero, S., and Rocktäschel, T. (2023). Promptbreeder: Self-referential self-improvement via prompt evolution. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2309.16797*.
- Glaser, B. G. and Strauss, A. L. (1967). *The Discovery of Grounded Theory: Strategies for Qualitative Research*. Aldine de Gruyter.
- He, J. et al. (2024). Does prompt formatting have any impact on LLM performance? *arXiv preprint arXiv:2411.10541*.
- Hu, E. J., Shen, Y., Wallis, P., Allen-Zhu, Z., Li, Y., Wang, S., Wang, L., and Chen, W. (2021). LoRA: Low-rank adaptation of large language models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2106.09685*.
- Ji, Z., Lee, N., Frieske, R., Yu, T., Su, D., Xu, Y., Ishii, E., Bang, Y. J., Madotto, A., and Fung, P. (2023). Survey of hallucination in natural language generation. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 55(12):1–38.
- Kamble, K., Russak, M., Mozolevskiy, D., Ali, M., Russak, M., and AlShikh, W. (2025). Expect the unexpected: FailSafe long context QA for finance. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2502.06329*.
- Khattab, O., Singhvi, A., Maheshwari, P., Zhang, Z., Santhanam, K., Vardhamanan, S., Haq, S., Sharma, A., Joshi, T. T., Mober, H., et al. (2024). DSPy: Compiling declarative language model calls into self-improving pipelines. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.03714*.
- Landis, J. R. and Koch, G. G. (1977). The measurement of observer agreement for categorical data. *Biometrics*, 33(1):159–174.

- Lee, J., Stevens, N., Han, S. C., and Song, M. (2024). A survey of large language models in finance (FinLLMs). *arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.02315*.
- Li, Y. et al. (2024). Large language models in finance: A survey. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2311.10723*.
- Liang, P., Bommasani, R., Lee, T., Tsipras, D., Soylu, D., Yasunaga, M., Zhang, Y., Narayanan, D., Wu, Y., Kumar, A., et al. (2023). Holistic evaluation of language models. *Transactions on Machine Learning Research*.
- Lin, C.-Y. (2004). ROUGE: A package for automatic evaluation of summaries. In *Text Summarization Branches Out*, pages 74–81.
- Lin, S., Hilton, J., and Evans, O. (2022). TruthfulQA: Measuring how models mimic human falsehoods. *Proceedings of the 60th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, pages 3214–3252.
- Mahdavi, S., Chen, J., Joshi, P. K., Guativa, L. H., and Singh, U. (2025). Integrating large language models in financial investments and market analysis: A survey. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2507.01990*.
- Mao, Y., He, J., and Chen, C. (2025). From prompts to templates: A systematic prompt template analysis for real-world LLMapps. In *Proceedings of the 33rd ACM International Conference on the Foundations of Software Engineering*. ACM.
- Nie, Y. et al. (2024). A survey of large language models for financial applications: Progress, prospects and challenges. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2406.11903*.
- Papineni, K., Roukos, S., Ward, T., and Zhu, W.-J. (2002). BLEU: A method for automatic evaluation of machine translation. In *Proceedings of the 40th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, pages 311–318.
- PoetiQ AI (2025). PoetiQ meta-system: Orchestration layer achieving state-of-the-art on reasoning benchmarks. https://poetiQ.ai/posts/arcagi_verified/. ARC Prize officially verified 54% on ARC-AGI-2 Semi-Private Test Set, December 2025.
- Ravi, S. S., Mielczarek, B., Kannappan, A., Kiela, D., and Qian, R. (2024). Lynx: An open source hallucination evaluation model. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.08488*.
- Schulhoff, S., Ilie, M., Balepur, N., Kahadze, K., Liu, A., Si, C., Li, Y., Gupta, A., Han, H., Schulhoff, S., et al. (2024). The prompt report: A systematic survey of prompting techniques. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2406.06608*.
- Suzgun, M. and Kalai, A. T. (2024). Meta-prompting: Enhancing language models with task-agnostic scaffolding. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.12954*.
- Wang, M. et al. (2024). LangGPT: Rethinking structured reusable prompt design framework for LLMs from the programming language. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.16929*.
- Wang, X., Wei, J., Schuurmans, D., Le, Q., Chi, E., Narang, S., Chowdhery, A., and Zhou, D. (2022). Self-consistency improves chain of thought reasoning in language models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2203.11171*.
- Wataoka, K., Aihara, T., Uchiyama, R., and Fujii, M. (2024). Self-preference bias in LLM-as-a-judge. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2404.13076*.

- Wei, J., Wang, X., Schuurmans, D., Bosma, M., Ichter, B., Xia, F., Chi, E., Le, Q., and Zhou, D. (2022). Chain-of-thought prompting elicits reasoning in large language models. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 35:24824–24837.
- Wu, S., Irsoy, O., Lu, S., Dabrovolski, V., Dredze, M., Gehrmann, S., Kambadur, P., Rosenberg, D., and Mann, G. (2023). BloombergGPT: A large language model for finance. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2303.17564*.
- Yang, H., Liu, X.-Y., and Wang, C. D. (2023). FinGPT: Open-source financial large language models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2306.06031*.
- Yao, S., Yu, D., Zhao, J., Shafran, I., Griffiths, T. L., Cao, Y., and Narasimhan, K. (2023). Tree of thoughts: Deliberate problem solving with large language models. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 36.
- Ye, J. et al. (2024). Justice or prejudice? quantifying biases in LLM-as-a-judge. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2410.02736*.
- Zheng, L., Chiang, W.-L., Sheng, Y., Zhuang, S., Wu, Z., Zhuang, Y., Lin, Z., Li, Z., Li, D., Xing, E. P., et al. (2023). Judging LLM-as-a-judge with MT-Bench and Chatbot Arena. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 36.
- Zhou, D., Schärli, N., Hou, L., Wei, J., Scales, N., Wang, X., Schuurmans, D., Cui, C., Bousquet, O., Le, Q., and Chi, E. (2022a). Least-to-most prompting enables complex reasoning in large language models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2205.10625*.
- Zhou, Y., Muresanu, A. I., Han, Z., Paster, K., Pitis, S., Chan, H., and Ba, J. (2022b). Large language models are human-level prompt engineers. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2211.01910*.
- Zhu, K., Wang, J., Zhou, J., Wang, Z., Chen, H., Wang, Y., Yang, L., Ye, W., Zhang, Y., Gong, N. Z., and Xie, X. (2023). PromptBench: Towards evaluating the robustness of large language models on adversarial prompts. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2306.04528*.

A. Complete Prompt Templates

All eight templates used in the experiment are reproduced below in their exact form. The placeholder `{case_data}` is replaced at runtime with the formatted case profile. Examples in Few-shot and ACTFIT templates are exclusive — they do not appear in the 60-case evaluation dataset.

A.1 Baseline (Zero-shot)

Direct instruction without persona, examples, or structural elements.

Template A.1.1: Baseline (Zero-shot) — Insurance Risk Classification

```
Classify the following life insurance applicant into one of four risk categories: Preferred,
↪ Standard, Substandard, or Declined.
```

```
Provide your classification and a brief justification based on the applicant's risk factors.
```

```
Applicant data:
{case_data}
```

Template A.1.2: Baseline (Zero-shot) — Portfolio Allocation

Recommend a portfolio allocation for the following investor. Specify percentages for each of
 ↪ these four asset classes, totaling 100%:

- Fixed Income (bonds, CDBs, government securities)
- Equities (domestic stocks, equity ETFs)
- Real Estate Funds (FIIIs)
- International Assets (BDRs, international ETFs)

Provide your allocation and a brief justification.

Investor data:
 {case_data}

A.2 Few-shot (2 examples)

Direct instruction with 2 worked examples (1 simple + 1 medium/diagnostic).

Template A.2.1: Few-shot (2 examples) — Insurance Risk Classification

Classify the following life insurance applicant into one of four risk categories: Preferred,
 ↪ Standard, Substandard, or Declined.

Provide your classification and a brief justification based on the applicant’s risk factors.

Here are two examples of how to perform this classification:

EXAMPLE 1:

Applicant: Female, age 28. Non-smoker. BMI 22. No pre-existing conditions. No family history
 ↪ of chronic disease. Occupation: software engineer. Regular physical activity (4x/week).
 ↪ No hazardous hobbies.

Classification: Preferred
 Justification: Young applicant with no adverse risk factors. Healthy BMI, non-smoker, no
 ↪ medical history, and low-risk occupation. All indicators align with the lowest risk
 ↪ category.

EXAMPLE 2:

Applicant: Male, age 55. Former smoker (quit 3 years ago). BMI 31 (obese). Type 2 diabetes
 ↪ diagnosed 5 years ago, controlled with metformin. Father died of heart attack at age
 ↪ 60. Occupation: truck driver. Sedentary lifestyle.

Classification: Substandard
 Justification: Multiple compounding risk factors: obesity, controlled but present diabetes,
 ↪ family history of cardiovascular disease, recent smoking history (quit < 5 years), high
 ↪ -risk occupation with sedentary pattern. Each factor individually might allow Standard;
 ↪ combined, they push into Substandard. Not Declined because diabetes is controlled and
 ↪ smoking has ceased.

Now classify this applicant:

Applicant data:
{case_data}

Template A.2.2: Few-shot (2 examples) — Portfolio Allocation

Recommend a portfolio allocation for the following investor. Specify percentages for each of
 ↪ these four asset classes, totaling 100%:

- Fixed Income (bonds, CDBs, government securities)
- Equities (domestic stocks, equity ETFs)
- Real Estate Funds (FIIIs)
- International Assets (BDRs, international ETFs)

Provide your allocation and a brief justification.

Here are two examples of how to perform this allocation:

EXAMPLE 1:

Investor: Female, age 35. Monthly income: R\$12,000. Risk profile: moderate. Investment goal:
 ↪ buy a property. Time horizon: 18 months. No existing investments. Emergency fund:
 ↪ already established (6 months of expenses in savings account).

Allocation:

- Fixed Income: 95%
- Equities: 0%
- Real Estate Funds: 0%
- International Assets: 5%

Justification: With an 18-month time horizon for a specific purchase goal, capital
 ↪ preservation is the absolute priority regardless of the investor’s moderate risk
 ↪ profile. The time horizon is too short to absorb equity or real estate volatility. 95%
 ↪ in fixed income (preferably low-duration instruments like Tesouro Selic or CDB with
 ↪ matching maturity) ensures the capital is available when needed. A small 5% allocation
 ↪ to international fixed-income ETFs provides minimal diversification without meaningful
 ↪ risk.

EXAMPLE 2:

Investor: Male, age 29. Monthly income: R\$8,000. Risk profile: aggressive. Investment goal:
 ↪ save for a wedding. Time horizon: 14 months. Current portfolio: R\$15,000 in stocks (
 ↪ IBOV ETF). Emergency fund: 3 months of expenses.

Allocation:

- Fixed Income: 95%
- Equities: 5%
- Real Estate Funds: 0%
- International Assets: 0%

Justification: Despite the aggressive risk profile, the 14-month time horizon for a defined-
 ↪ date goal (wedding) requires capital preservation. The investor should reallocate most
 ↪ of the existing equity position into fixed income instruments maturing near the wedding
 ↪ date. Maintaining 5% in equities acknowledges the aggressive profile minimally but

```

    ↪ does not compromise the goal. The time horizon overrides the risk profile when a
    ↪ specific, near-term objective exists.
---
Now allocate for this investor:

Investor data:
{case_data}

```

A.3 CRISPE

Structured roleplay framework: Capacity, Role, Insight, Statement, Personality, Experiment.

Template A.3.1: CRISPE — Insurance Risk Classification

```

**Capacity:** You are capable of analyzing medical, demographic, and lifestyle data to assess
    ↪ mortality risk and classify life insurance applicants.

**Role:** Act as a senior life insurance underwriter with 20 years of experience in the
    ↪ Brazilian market, specializing in individual risk assessment.

**Insight:** Life insurance risk classification is based on mortality risk factors including
    ↪ age, medical history, family history, lifestyle habits (smoking, alcohol, exercise),
    ↪ occupation, BMI, and existing conditions. The four standard categories are:
- Preferred: Lowest risk, best health profile, favorable pricing.
- Standard: Average risk, minor factors present, standard pricing.
- Substandard: Elevated risk, significant factors present, loaded premium.
- Declined: Risk too high, application rejected.
Factors are evaluated both individually and in combination --- compounding factors increase
    ↪ severity.

**Statement:** Classify the following life insurance applicant into exactly one of the four
    ↪ categories (Preferred, Standard, Substandard, or Declined). Provide the classification
    ↪ and a justification citing the specific risk factors that determined your decision.

**Personality:** Be analytical and conservative. When in doubt between two adjacent categories,
    ↪ favor the higher-risk classification. Insurance underwriting prioritizes loss
    ↪ prevention.

**Experiment:** After your primary classification, briefly note whether the applicant is a
    ↪ borderline case that might shift to an adjacent category under different underwriting
    ↪ guidelines, and explain why.

Applicant data:
{case_data}

```

Template A.3.2: CRISPE — Portfolio Allocation

```

**Capacity:** You are capable of analyzing investor profiles and recommending asset allocation
    ↪ strategies based on risk assessment, time horizon analysis, and portfolio construction
    ↪ principles.

**Role:** Act as a certified financial planner (CFP) with 15 years of experience in the
    ↪ Brazilian wealth management market, specializing in individual portfolio construction.

```

```

**Insight:** Portfolio allocation in the Brazilian market typically uses four main asset
    ↪ classes:
    - Fixed Income: Tesouro Direto, CDBs, LCIs/LCAs, debentures. Low risk, predictable returns.
    - Equities: Stocks (B3), equity ETFs. Higher risk, higher long-term return potential.
    - Real Estate Funds (FIIs): Listed real estate investment trusts. Income-generating, moderate
      ↪ risk.
    - International Assets: BDRs, international ETFs. Diversification benefit, currency exposure.

Key allocation principles include matching investment horizon to asset risk, diversifying
    ↪ across uncorrelated classes, and considering the investor's total financial picture
    ↪ including emergency reserves. Time horizon is a critical factor --- short-term goals
    ↪ generally require more conservative allocations.

**Statement:** Recommend a portfolio allocation for the following investor. Specify
    ↪ percentages for each of the four asset classes above, totaling exactly 100%. Provide
    ↪ the allocation and a justification explaining the reasoning behind each percentage.

**Personality:** Be methodical and client-focused. Prioritize capital preservation for near-
    ↪ term goals and growth for long-term horizons. Communicate clearly, avoiding jargon. Be
    ↪ decisive --- recommend specific percentages, not ranges.

**Experiment:** After your primary recommendation, briefly note one alternative allocation the
    ↪ investor might consider if their time horizon were to change significantly (e.g.,
    ↪ extended by 3+ years), and explain how that would shift the allocation.

Investor data:
{case_data}
    
```

A.4 ACTFIT

Institutional governance framework: Agent, Context, Task, Format, Illustration, Tone.

Template A.4.1: ACTFIT — Insurance Risk Classification

```

## Agent
You are a senior actuarial analyst specialized in life insurance underwriting. Your expertise
    ↪ includes:
    - Mortality risk factor analysis (medical, demographic, behavioral)
    - Brazilian insurance market standards and SUSEP regulatory environment
    - Systematic multi-factor risk assessment methodology
    - Conservative underwriting principles: when evidence is ambiguous, classify toward higher
      ↪ risk

You apply structured, evidence-based reasoning. Every classification must be traceable to
    ↪ specific risk factors in the applicant's profile. You never fabricate or assume data
    ↪ not present in the profile --- if information is missing, you flag it explicitly.

## Context
You operate in the Brazilian individual life insurance market. Your classifications directly
    ↪ determine premium pricing and policy terms.

**Business impact of errors:**
    
```

```

- Classifying too leniently (e.g., Substandard as Standard) --> adverse selection, increased
  ↳ claims, portfolio losses
- Classifying too strictly (e.g., Standard as Substandard) --> lost business, competitive
  ↳ disadvantage

**Classification categories (mutually exclusive):**
- **Preferred**: Excellent health profile, no significant risk factors, lowest mortality risk
- **Standard**: Average risk, minor factors present but well-controlled, standard mortality
  ↳ tables apply
- **Substandard**: Elevated risk due to significant medical, behavioral, or occupational
  ↳ factors, premium loading required
- **Declined**: Risk exceeds acceptable thresholds for individual underwriting, policy cannot
  ↳ be issued

**Compounding rule:** Multiple moderate risk factors in combination may elevate classification
  ↳ beyond what any single factor would warrant.

## Task
Analyze the applicant profile provided below and perform the following:
1. Identify all relevant risk factors present in the profile
2. Assess each factor's individual severity (low / moderate / high)
3. Evaluate compounding effects between factors
4. Assign exactly ONE classification category
5. Flag any missing information that could affect the classification

## Format
Structure your response EXACTLY as follows:

CLASSIFICATION: [Preferred / Standard / Substandard / Declined]

RISK FACTORS IDENTIFIED:
- [Factor 1]: [severity] --- [brief note]
- [Factor 2]: [severity] --- [brief note]
(list all relevant factors)

COMPOUNDING EFFECTS: [Describe how factors interact, or "None --- factors are independent"]

JUSTIFICATION: [2-3 sentences explaining why this classification and not an adjacent one]

MISSING INFORMATION: [List any data not in the profile that would improve accuracy, or "None
  ↳ --- profile is complete"]

## Illustration
Example of expected output structure and reasoning:

For an applicant who is male, age 47, non-smoker, BMI 26, controlled hypertension (lisinopril),
  ↳ sedentary lifestyle, office worker, no family history:

CLASSIFICATION: Standard

RISK FACTORS IDENTIFIED:
- Hypertension: moderate --- controlled with medication but still present as chronic condition
- BMI 26: low --- slightly overweight but within acceptable range
- Sedentary lifestyle: low-moderate --- contributes to cardiovascular risk over time
    
```

```

- Age 47: low --- approaching higher-risk decades but currently within normal range

COMPOUNDING EFFECTS: Sedentary lifestyle combined with controlled hypertension creates mild
  ↳ cardiovascular risk elevation, but medication control mitigates the compounding effect.

JUSTIFICATION: Individual risk factors are each moderate or below. Hypertension is the primary
  ↳ driver, but it is well-controlled. The profile does not meet Preferred criteria due to
  ↳ the chronic condition, but compounding effects are insufficient for Substandard.
  ↳ Standard classification is appropriate.

MISSING INFORMATION: Cholesterol levels, blood glucose, and detailed cardiac history would
  ↳ improve assessment accuracy.

## Tone
Technical and precise. Use clinical and actuarial language. Commit to a single classification
  ↳ --- do not hedge with "could be X or Y." Every statement must be grounded in the
  ↳ applicant's data. If information is absent, state that it is absent rather than
  ↳ assuming.

---

Applicant data:
{case_data}

```

Template A.4.2: ACTFIT — Portfolio Allocation

```

## Agent
You are a senior portfolio strategist specialized in individual wealth management in the
  ↳ Brazilian market. Your expertise includes:
- Term-based portfolio construction (matching asset risk to investment horizon)
- Risk profiling and suitability analysis under CVM/ANBIMA guidelines
- Asset allocation across fixed income, equities, real estate, and international classes
- Behavioral finance awareness: identifying when investor preferences conflict with financial
  ↳ prudence

You apply disciplined, evidence-based allocation. Every percentage must be justified by the
  ↳ investor's time horizon, risk profile, and financial situation. You never recommend
  ↳ allocations that expose near-term goals to inappropriate volatility.

## Context
You operate in the Brazilian individual investment market. Your recommendations directly
  ↳ affect clients' ability to meet financial goals.

**Core allocation principle --- TIME HORIZON DOMINATES RISK PROFILE:**
- Short-term goals ( $\leq 2$  years): Fixed Income must be 90-100%, regardless of stated risk
  ↳ profile. The rationale is mathematical: equity and real estate volatility over periods
  ↳ under 2 years can result in capital loss precisely when funds are needed.
- Medium-term goals (3-7 years): Allocation depends on risk profile within defined bands.
  ↳ Conservative: Fixed Income 70-85%. Moderate: Fixed Income 50-70%. Aggressive: Fixed
  ↳ Income 40-55%.
- Long-term goals (8+ years): Greater diversification appropriate. Conservative: Fixed Income
  ↳ 50-65%. Moderate: Fixed Income 35-50%. Aggressive: Fixed Income 20-35%.

**Asset classes (must total 100%):**

```

- **Fixed Income**: Tesouro Direto, CDBs, LCIs/LCAs, debentures. Capital preservation and ↪ predictable returns.
- **Equities**: B3 stocks, equity ETFs. Growth potential, higher volatility.
- **Real Estate Funds (FIIs)**: Listed REITs. Income generation, moderate volatility. Minimum ↪ recommended horizon: 3+ years.
- **International Assets**: BDRs, international ETFs. Currency diversification, global ↪ exposure. Recommended: 5-20% for medium/long-term portfolios.

Critical suitability rules:

- Emergency fund must exist before any non-fixed-income allocation. If absent, recommend ↪ establishing it first.
- Existing portfolio positions must be considered --- recommend transitions, not greenfield ↪ allocations in isolation.
- When investor's stated risk profile conflicts with their time horizon, prioritize time ↪ horizon and explain why.

Task

Analyze the investor profile provided below and perform the following:

1. Identify the time horizon category (short / medium / long-term)
2. Assess the investor's risk profile in context of their goal and situation
3. Check for conflicts between risk profile and time horizon
4. Assign specific percentages for each of the 4 asset classes (totaling 100%)
5. Flag any missing information or financial health concerns

Format

Structure your response EXACTLY as follows:

TIME HORIZON: [X months/years] --> Category: [Short-term / Medium-term / Long-term]

RISK ASSESSMENT: [Stated profile] | [Effective profile after time horizon adjustment, if ↪ different]

ALLOCATION:

- Fixed Income: [X]%
 - Equities: [X]%
 - Real Estate Funds: [X]%
 - International Assets: [X]%
- (Total: 100%)

JUSTIFICATION: [3-4 sentences explaining the allocation logic, especially any adjustments due ↪ to time horizon constraints]

FLAGS: [Any concerns about emergency fund, existing portfolio, or profile-horizon conflicts. " ↪ None" if clean.]

Illustration

Example of expected output structure and reasoning:

For an investor who is male, age 40, monthly income R\$15,000, aggressive risk profile, goal of ↪ funding children's university education, time horizon 5 years, existing portfolio R\$80 ↪ ,000 (70% equities, 30% fixed income), emergency fund fully established:

TIME HORIZON: 5 years --> Category: Medium-term

```

RISK ASSESSMENT: Aggressive | Adjusted to moderate-aggressive --- 5-year horizon constrains
    ↪ full aggressive allocation

ALLOCATION:
- Fixed Income: 50%
- Equities: 25%
- Real Estate Funds: 15%
- International Assets: 10%
(Total: 100%)

JUSTIFICATION: The 5-year medium-term horizon permits equity exposure but requires meaningful
    ↪ fixed income anchor. Although the investor's stated profile is aggressive, the specific
    ↪ and non-negotiable nature of the goal (children's education) warrants a more
    ↪ conservative tilt. Current portfolio is over-exposed to equities (70%) for this horizon
    ↪ and should be gradually rebalanced. FII allocation provides income component;
    ↪ international provides currency diversification.

FLAGS: Current portfolio (70% equities) is misaligned with 5-year education goal. Recommend
    ↪ phased rebalancing over 6-12 months to avoid tax events from sudden liquidation.

## Tone
Methodical and client-centric. Use clear financial reasoning accessible to the investor. Be
    ↪ decisive --- assign specific percentages, not ranges. When overriding the investor's
    ↪ stated risk preference due to time horizon, explain the rationale respectfully but
    ↪ firmly. Ground every recommendation in the investor's actual data.

---

Investor data:
{case_data}
    
```

B. Dataset Summary

The experiment uses 60 cases across two financial domains, each with professional-grade ground truth. Complete case profiles with ground truth labels and justifications are available in the public replication repository (`dataset_seguros.json` and `dataset_invest.json`).

B.1 Insurance Risk Classification (30 cases)

Each case presents a life insurance applicant profile with demographic, medical, lifestyle, and occupational data. Ground truth classifications follow actuarial underwriting criteria, where multiple moderate risk factors in combination may elevate classification beyond what any single factor warrants.

Table B.1: Insurance Dataset Distribution

Complexity	N	Preferred	Standard	Substandard	Declined
Simple	10	5	3	0	2
Medium	12	0	8	3	1
Difficult	8	0	2	6	0
Total	30	5	13	9	3

Simple cases present unambiguous risk profiles. Medium cases involve chronic conditions under treatment or compounding moderate factors. Difficult cases include borderline classifications where reasonable underwriters might disagree — testicular cancer in long-term remission, well-controlled Type 1 diabetes, metabolically healthy obesity, or unscreened familial hypertrophic cardiomyopathy.

B.2 Portfolio Allocation (30 cases)

Each case presents an investor profile including income, risk tolerance, investment goal, time horizon, existing portfolio, and emergency fund status. Ground truth follows the time-horizon-dominates-risk-profile principle: short-term goals (≤ 2 years) require 90–100% fixed income regardless of stated risk preference.

Table B.2: Investment Dataset Distribution

Complexity	N	Short-term	Medium-term	Long-term	Mixed
Simple	10	10	0	0	0
Medium	12	1	10	1	0
Difficult	8	2	2	1	3
Total	30	13	12	2	3

Difficult investment cases test whether models can override stated risk preferences when time horizons demand capital preservation, recognize dual-horizon portfolios requiring bucket strategies, or prioritize human welfare over standard allocation advice — such as an unemployed investor burning savings or an elderly pensioner with a monthly income deficit.

B.3 Calibration Cases

Two calibration cases per task (INS-S03, INS-M05, INV-S04, INV-M06) were used to verify judge scoring alignment before full evaluation. These cases remain in the dataset and are scored normally.

C. Replication Repository

All experimental materials are publicly available at:

<https://github.com/hirbis/prompt-governance>

Archived with DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18727949>

The repository contains the following components for full replication:

- `run_experiment.py` — Main experiment script: constructs prompts, executes API calls across all 2,160 configurations, and records raw responses with metadata (tokens, latency, timestamps).
- `evaluate_with_judges.py` — LLM-as-Judge evaluation: sends each response to both judges (Claude Opus 4.6 and GPT-4o) with domain-specific evaluation prompts and records binary scores.

- `calculate_metrics_fixed.py` — Metric computation: applies conservative consensus protocol, calculates accuracy, hallucination, consistency, and Efficiency Score by all groupings reported in the paper.
- `prompts.py` — All 8 prompt templates (4 frameworks \times 2 tasks) in their exact experimental form.
- `dataset_seguros.json`, `dataset_invest.json` — Complete datasets (60 cases) with ground truth labels and justifications.
- `scored_results.jsonl` — Raw scored results from both judges for all 2,158 evaluated responses.
- `human_validation_form_BLIND.xlsx` — Human validation form (blinded: without judge scores, to avoid anchoring bias in independent replication).

Dependencies, environment setup, and execution instructions are provided in the repository README.

D. Model Selection Transparency Note

During the experimental setup phase, model selection was updated due to API availability changes:

Original Model	Status	Replacement	Rationale
Claude 3.5 Sonnet	Retired by Anthropic (NotFoundError on API)	Claude Sonnet 4.5 (<code>claude-sonnet4520250929</code>)	Direct successor, same family
GPT-4o (originally planned) / GPT-5 (tested as alternative)	GPT-5 is a reasoning model that does not accept temperature parameter	GPT-4.1 (<code>gpt4.120250414</code>)	Maintains parametric parity (temperature + max_tokens)
Gemini 2.5 Flash (Preview)	Maintained	Gemini 2.5 Flash (<code>gemini-2.5-flash</code>)	Stable version used

These substitutions were made before data collection began. No data were discarded or recollected due to the changes.